
Technical report on state-of-the-art of value chain scenario assessment

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

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Approvals

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	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
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	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Objective	2
1.2 Scope	2
1.3 Outline of the Methodology	3
1.4 Positioning of the Report in the CIRC-PACK Project Tasks	3
2 Value Chain Concept and Assessment Methodologies	5
2.1 Value Chain Concept	5
2.2 Value Chain Analysis	5
2.3 Packaging Value Chain.....	8
2.4 Methodologies to Measure Circular Economy	11
2.5 Life Cycle Approach	14
2.6 Life Cycle Approach for the Assessment of Value Chains	18
3 Sustainability and Circularity Indicators	20
3.1 General Properties of the Indicators	20
3.1.1 SMART Criteria.....	20
3.1.2 RACER Criteria	21
3.2 Sustainability Indicator Sets.....	22
3.2.1 UN Sustainable Development Goals Indicators	22
3.2.2 UNEP Sustainable Consumption and Production Headline Indicators.....	26
3.2.3 European Benchmark Indicators.....	28
3.2.4 Sustainable Development Indicators.....	30
3.2.5 Indicators used for the Environmental Policy Review.....	33
3.2.6 European Environment Agency Core Indicator Set.....	35
3.2.7 Ecosystem-based Indices for Industries	36
3.2.8 Composite Indices for Industries	39
3.2.9 FP7 and H2020 Projects	41
3.3 Environmental Indicators.....	45
3.3.1 Resource Efficiency Indicators	45
3.3.2 Waste and Emission Indicators.....	49
3.3.3 LCA Indicators	51

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

3.4	Economic Indicators	56
3.5	Social Indicators	58
3.6	Circularity Indicators	65
3.6.1	Linear Flow/Circular Flow Index	65
3.6.2	Product Utility	65
3.6.3	Material Circularity Indicator.....	66
3.6.4	Resource Productivity.....	67
3.6.5	Value-based Resource Efficiency	67
3.6.6	Resource Duration / Longevity	68
4	Decision Support Tools.....	69
5	Circular Economy and Industrial Symbiosis Good Practices	75
5.1	China's Use of Circular Economy Indicators.....	75
5.2	Japan's Recycle-Oriented Society and Use of Indicators.....	76
6	Potential for Replication under CIRC-PACK Project	78
6.1	Evaluation and Relevancy of Indicators to CIRC-PACK Project	78
6.1.1	Relevancy of Indicators to CIRC-PACK	78
6.1.2	Evaluation of Indicators	88
6.1.3	Recommendations for Further Studies on Indicators	91
6.2	Evaluation of Assessment Methodologies and Applicability to CIRC-PACK	92
6.3	Evaluation of Decision Support Tools	94
7	Conclusions	97
	References.....	99
	ANNEX: RACER ASSESSMENT CRITERIA AND SUB-CRITERIA EXPLAINED	106

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CIRC-PACK:	Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain
CAPEX:	Capital cost
CE	Circular Economy
CEIS	Circular Economy Indicator System (CEIS)
CSPI:	Composite Sustainable Development Index
DC	Demo Case
DPSIR:	Driver, Pressure, State, Impact, Response (Framework)
EMF	Ellen McArthur Foundation
EPSM:	Environmental performance strategy map
EPR:	Environmental policy review
ETV:	Environmental Technology Verification
EBI:	European Benchmark Indicator
EEA:	European Environment Agency
EU:	European Union
FP:	Framework Programme
GHG:	Greenhouse gases
GDP:	Gross Domestic Product
LCA:	Life cycle assessment
LCC:	Life cycle costing
LFI	Linear Flow Index
MCI	Material Circularity Indicator
MIPS:	Material input per unit service
NPV:	Net present value
OPEX:	Operational cost
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RACER	Relevant, Accepted, Credible, Easy, Robust
ROI:	Return on investment
SRM:	Secondary raw material
S-LCA:	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, Time-bound
SPI:	Sustainability performance index
SCP:	Sustainable consumption and production
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDI:	Sustainable development indicators
SDS:	Sustainable development strategy
SEPI:	Sustainable environment performance indicator
UN	United Nations
VC	Value Chain
VCA	Value Chain Analysis
WP	Work Package

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 2.1 (Technical Report on State-of-the-Art of Value Chain Scenario Assessment) is prepared under the CIRC-PACK Project as the main output of Task 2.1 on Background and alignment of CIRC-PACK evaluation methodology. This deliverable provides the baseline for the assessment methodology for evaluation of the improvements provided by CIRC-PACK value chain to be developed in Task 2.2. This report will also facilitate Tasks 2.3, 2.4, 2.5 and Work Package 6.

The objectives of this deliverable are:

- (i) providing an overview of existing sustainability (environmental, economic and social) and circularity indicators
- (ii) evaluation of good practices of circular economy and industrial symbiosis and related decision support tools
- (iii) analysing the existing practices for value chain scenario assessment methodologies with respect to their potential for replication under CIRC-PACK (i.e., the circular plastics packaging value chain)
- (iv) deliver a preliminary list of indicators with high relevance to assessment of CIRC-PACK value chain

Value chain analysis, life cycle approach and circular economy assessment is covered and core principles of CEIS methodology is commented. Value chain analysis enables identification of each step/actor in the value chain and their added values which is very crucial for a complex and multi-sectorial system as CIRC-PACK. Life cycle thinking should definitely be included in the methodology by improving the approach from cradle-to-grave to cradle-to-cradle which is more compatible with circular economy concept. It is also suggested to set a framework specific to circularity assessment methodology of CIRC- PACK by identifying processes to monitor, involved actors, requirements to be measured and implementation level.

Indicators are embraced under three pillars of sustainability (environmental, economic and social) and circularity. While determining the relevancy level of indicators to CIRC-PACK CEIS methodology, expert decisions are made considering the objectives and expected impacts of CIRC-PACK project as well as foreseen impacts of transition of plastics packaging value chain from linear to circular. Evaluation of SMART and RACER criteria should be performed in more details within Task 2.2 parallel to indicator selection process.

Evaluation of existing circularity assessment tools revealed some conceptual suggestions for the tool to be developed under CIRC-PACK project in terms of its baseline, flexibility, ease of use and coverage.

Deliverable 2.1 provides a comprehensive baseline and preliminary evaluation on assessment methodologies, sustainability and circularity indicators and decision support tools that will strongly facilitate the upcoming tasks of CIRC-PACK project.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

1 INTRODUCTION

Production of plastics is expected to be doubled in 20 years, in parallel with its increasing application fields [1]. In Europe, packaging applications represent 39.9% of the total plastics demand as the largest application field for the plastics industry in 2015 [2]. This increasing production and consumption of plastics puts pressure on the environment in terms of resource depletion (i.e., oil), greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) emissions and water pollution due to leakage of plastics to the oceans [1].

Ellen McArthur Foundation (EMF) defines the Circular Economy (CE) concept as “A circular economy is a global economic model that aims to decouple economic growth and development from the consumption of finite resources. Increasingly, companies see tremendous opportunity in this model, as it not only allows them to capture additional value from their products and materials, but also to mitigate risks from material price volatility and material supply.” [3]. EMF also sets three main ambitions to move to a circular plastic packaging value chain defined by [4]:

- i. Create an effective after-use plastics economy by improving the economics and uptake of recycling, reuse and controlled biodegradation for targeted applications.
- ii. Drastically reduce leakage of plastics into natural systems (in particular, the ocean) and other negative externalities.
- iii. Decouple plastics from fossil feedstock by – in addition to reducing cycle losses and dematerialising – exploring and adopting renewably sourced feedstock.

CIRC-PACK (Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain) project aims to develop innovation actions that addresses the ambitious targets set by EMF and thus contributing to United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and European Union (EU) circular economy targets in a broader perspective.

Although several publications can be found on circular economy, there is a lack of studies and frameworks that focuses on effective measurement of circularity, including tools and criteria, of a product, service or a supply chain [5].

In order to achieve and monitor a successful evolution towards a more circular economy, applicable methods and tools are needed to be developed. This methods and tools should aim to inform policy and decision making and to assist industrial practitioners (such as engineers, designers, managers) for the proper measurement and quantification of circularity improvements [6][7]. Utilising indicators for this purpose is favourable due to their ability to summarise, focus and intensify the complexity of our dynamic environment into a meaningful information in manageable amount [8]. Associating indicator metrics with life cycle thinking approach would be complementary to assess the transition from a linear economy to a more circular one.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

1.1 Objective

The objectives of this deliverable are to:

- (v) provide an overview of existing sustainability (environmental, economic and social) indicators as well as circularity indicators
- (vi) evaluate good practices of circular economy and industrial symbiosis and related decision support tools
- (vii) analyse the existing practices for value chain scenario assessment methodologies with respect to their potential for replication under CIRC-PACK (i.e., the circular plastics packaging value chain)
- (viii) deliver a preliminary list of indicators with high relevance to assessment of CIRC-PACK value chain

1.2 Scope

As a technical state-of-the-art report, the scope of this document starts with a detailed literature search on indicators, decision support tools, assessment methodologies and then provides a preliminary evaluation in accordance with the CIRC-PACK objectives and illustrates several good practices as well. This report is structured as described in the following paragraph and summarized in Figure 1:

Section 2 introduces the value chain concept and value chain analysis. Giving brief information on packaging value chain and plastics in specific, it is concluded by providing an overview of life cycle assessment framework including Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) methodologies. *Section 3* focuses on the sustainability and circularity indicators. Existing indicator sets are given and circularity indicators as well as basic environmental, economic and social are compiled. *Section 4* summarizes decision support tools used for circular economy evaluation and indicator based assessments. *Section 5* includes some case studies and good practices of indicator based measurement of circular economy and industrial symbiosis. *Section 6* discusses the relevance and applicability of assessment methodologies, indicators and decision support tools given in Sections 2, 3 and 4 respectively. Finally, *Section 7* concludes the discussions into recommendations and further studies for the following tasks of CIRC-PACK project.

Figure 1 Structure and scope of the report

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

1.3 Outline of the Methodology

To achieve the objectives outlined in the previous section, a comprehensive literature review is the first step. Sustainability and circularity indicators, value chain assessment methods, good practices of circular economy or assessment methodologies and related decision support tools are reviewed and compiled. Several Horizon 2020 and Framework Programme 7 (FP7) projects have also been reviewed. Compiled information is used to analyse the potential of replication of these methodologies and indicators for CIRC-PACK value chain. Finally, highly relevant indicators are determined and recommendations are made for further tasks of the project, especially Task 2.2 in which Circular Economy Indicator System (CEIS) metrics will be developed. This methodology is summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Methodological overview of the report

1.4 Positioning of the Report in the CIRC-PACK Project Tasks

Task 2.1, with this report as the main output, plays a crucial role in the project actions related with the evaluation of the improvements provided by CIRC-PACK value chain.

This report will be the basis for Task 2.2, where the methodology for CIRC-PACK Demo Cases evaluation will be developed. Evaluation methodology will be based on Circular Economy Indicator System (CEIS) that enables the assessment of CIRC-PACK value chain in terms of environmental, social and economic performances. This methodology will then be utilized in Tasks 2.2 and 2.3 for preliminary assessment of CIRC-PACK value chain and demo case innovations. Moreover, a preliminary literature search and evaluation is being made for the

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

existing circularity assessment tools to facilitate Task 2.5 on Development of the CIRC-PACK interactive and dynamic virtual map.

Additionally, this report will also be an input for Work Package (WP) 6 on upscaling of CIRC-PACK solutions where the methodology developed in Task 2.2 will be used as well.

During the assessment of reviewed indicators and methodologies for their potential to be applied in CIRC-PACK, Demo Cases that will be handled in WP 3, WP 4 and WP 5 will be elaborated for a better understanding of the material flows in CIRC-PACK value chain.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

2 VALUE CHAIN CONCEPT AND ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGIES

2.1 Value Chain Concept

Value chain (VC) concept was first introduced by Porter (1998) as a chain of activities for transforming inputs into outputs in order to deliver value to the customer [9]. At industrial level, VC was defined as all industry participants, connected in a successive chain of value added: raw material production, original equipment manufacturer, customers, wholesalers, retailers, retail customers and even recycling [10].

Wang (2015) states that initially the *value* in a value chain was mainly monetary value, which is the difference between the final price the customer pays and the sum of the cost of all activities in VC. However, recently, non-monetary values regarding social and environmental dimensions are also integrated into economic aspect of VC. [11]

Porter (1998) classifies the nine activities of the value chain in two groups: 1) Primary activities directly involved in creating and adding value to the product, including inbound logistics, operations, outbound logistics, marketing and sales, and service. 2) Support activities, which are macro-environment driving forces providing assistance that enables and improves the performance of the primary activities: procurement, technology development, human resource management, and firm infrastructure [9].

Figure 3 Porter's value chain activities (adapted from [9])

2.2 Value Chain Analysis

Value chain analysis (VCA) has been utilized for several years to understand different sectors, particularly with respect to identifying constraints to growth and possible areas of intervention [12]. It focuses on the dynamics of inter-linkages within the productive sector, especially the way in which firms and countries are globally integrated [13].

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Value chain analysis have several advantages compared to traditional static sectoral analysis because it deals with dynamic linkages between productive activities that go beyond that particular sector;

- uncovers the dynamic flow of economic, organizational and coercive activities between producers within different sectors even on a global scale; and
- enables to understand the policy environment and to ensure more informed decision making [13].

VCA is a valuable tool to identify the need and scope for systematic competitiveness. Mapping the value chain enables a company to determine the external players whose activities have more influence on their success. Kaplinsky, R. and Morris, M. (2015) states that this methodology can also be used to demonstrate the impact of individual firms for national or regional economic management [13]. It can be deduced that this methodology is also applicable to analyse a sectorial value chain like plastic packaging to identify and indicate the added value from each value chain actor and their impacts in the circularity of the value chain.

Stages of VCA can be summarized in four stages [13][14][15]:

1. Mapping the value chain

In this stage, different steps and actors in a particular value chain are visualized. For an industrial plant or sector, flows (inputs and outputs) of principle materials are mapped. This provides a generic overview of the sector, as well as allowing a clear understanding between actors and/or process steps. Mapping of the value chain is a good exercise to determine who else's behaviour plays an important role in a firm's or product's success.

2. Value added

The second stage is to determine the monetary value added (i.e., the difference in the price of a material, mid-product or product between the stages of the value chain) at each step of (or by each actor in) the value chain. It is important to determine the value added in order to execute the distribution of income and benefits along the value chain.

3. Indicator set

Stage three is defining a set of indicators to address the challenges under consideration. Indicators are specific to sector and the objective of the particular study. Some examples of the indicators and how the results are designated in previous studies are given in Table 1.

4. Interpretation of the results

The interactions between process steps/actors and selected indicators are demonstrated in Stage 4 to interpret how the indicators influence the value chain. This helps to compare the impact vs. added value of each step (each process or sector) in a value chain for selected indicators. This identification enables to determine the measures to be taken or the actions for improving the success or competitiveness of a company or sector. This indication may be quantitative or qualitative and can be designated in tabular or graphical format.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Table 1 Examples of indicators selected for value chain analysis

Examples of indicators selected for value chain analysis		
Goal	Indicators	Reference
Examining the residual outputs generated by UK steel and aluminium industry and the value of reusing or recycling those products	Quantitative indicators to address economic aspect and environmental challenges: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Net import monetary value • Greenhouse gas emissions (tonnes CO₂-eq/tonnes product) • Waste landfilled (tonnes waste landfilled/tonnes product) 	[14]
To develop a method for applying VCA to the informal recycling sector in Zabaleen and conclude the possible improvements in the sector	Indicators to address technical and socio-economic challenges of the sector: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connections in the value chain • Waste valorisation Enabling environment	[15]
To relate the material flows to economic variables which also indicates sustainable resource management in the UK steel and aluminium value chains	Resource use indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource efficiency (resources used per unit production) • Energy efficiency (energy consumption per unit production) • Resource productivity (value added per unit resource used) Socio economic indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic labour productivity (value added per worker) • Material labour productivity (amount of material produced per worker) 	[16]
Evaluation of pond fish farming value chain in Egypt	Financial indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gross output (prices) values per kg • operational profits per tonne of fish produced or sold • net profits per tonne of fish produced or sold • total net value-added per tonne of fish sold • the percentage of the total operational profits Socio-economic indicators (based on employment creation) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • jobs created per 100 tonnes of sold product • the percentage of days contributed by 	[17]

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	<p>women</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the percentage of full-time jobs opposed to part-time or seasonal • the percentage of jobs created for those under-thirty years of age 	
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2.3 Packaging Value Chain

Sand (2010), in her book *The Packaging Value Chain*, compares supply chain management and value chain as a logistical function that addresses the transference of goods from the raw material state to the final consumer. In the value chain, however, the consumer determines the value; and industry endeavours to provide this value in a chain from the post-consumer environment to raw packaging materials. This integrated, non-linear value chain, where logistical functions and value functions coexist, and value is conveyed through the value chain is called as *interconnected value chain model*. This model applied to the packaging industry, indicates the connection to the consumer and the need for ensuring that the package being created has value. [18]

With the growing impact of increasing population densities, rising energy costs, and rapidly developing economies that demand more access to goods, these chains have to be circular. With the circular value chain approach, the interest in the design of more readily recyclable and reusable packaging materials is increasing. This results in a higher value of the post-consumer package for raw material suppliers. Figure 4 is compiled from Sand (2010) to demonstrate the transformation from linear supply chain approach first into an interconnected semicircle and then into a circular value chain approach. [18]

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment	
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version: 1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date: 31/8/17

Figure 4 Evolving Packaging Value Chain (compiled from [18])

New_InnoNet Project (The Near-Zero European Waste Innovation Network), funded by EU Horizon 2020 Programme (Waste, 642231), targets three value chains to establish a European platform for stakeholders aiming to show how the concept of circular economy can be enhanced and stimulated. One of the targeted value chains is plastic packaging. Operations, actors and material flows (products) in the plastic packaging value chain are demonstrated in Figure 5. [19]

As an output of New_InnoNet project, plastic packaging value chain is analysed to identify the bottlenecks that restrains the minimization of waste production within the value chain and to determine the potential benefits if these bottlenecks could be overcome.[19]

Figure 5 Plastic packaging waste value chain [19]

Actors in the plastic packaging value chain are waste suppliers (households, business and retailers), producer responsibility organisations, recyclers, plastic converters/processors manufacturing plastic products. Operations in the plastic packaging waste value chain are waste generation, collection, pre-treatment/sorting and processing which includes sorting, cleaning, grinding and melting. [19]

The products handled in plastic packaging waste value chain are waste packaging materials and recycled plastics to be used as raw material. The main obstacles for achieving a circular economy in plastic packaging value chain through EU are identified as [19]:

- Limited source separation,
- Bad product design,
- Export of plastic packaging waste outside the EU,
- Performance of separation/sorting technology,
- Performance of recycling technology.

To indicate the potential impacts of these bottlenecks, they are analysed separately and in several combination scenarios with respect to material efficiency (losses of plastics), economic (total costs, revenues and employment), environmental (GHG emissions), and other aspects (feasibility of removing the bottleneck) [13]. The results are given in below table.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Table 2 Analysis of the bottlenecks [19]

	Losses of plastics in the recycling system	Total EU cost of the recycling scenario	Total EU revenues	GHG emissions inside the EU	Employment		Feasibility for solving the bottleneck ²⁰
	%	€/ton recycled	€/ton recycled	kg CO ₂ eq/ton waste generated	Jobs/ton recycled	Total jobs	high (5), low (1)
Situation 2012	69%	1.474	676	1.143	79,5	30.979	-
Limited source separation of plastic packaging waste	52%	1.212	678	955	78,0	47.244	3
'Bad' product design	68%	1.425	676	1.126	77,6	31.735	1
Export of plastic packaging waste for recycling outside EU	69%	1.604	748	1.206	71,7	35.111	1
Performance of separation/sorting technology	68%	1.430	676	1.127	77,6	31.735	4
Performance of recycling technology	67%	1.408	679	1.121	74,3	30.952	5

2.4 Methodologies to Measure Circular Economy

Elia et. al. (2016) introduced a four-level framework for circular economy to be evaluated and measured: processes to monitor, actions involved, requirements to be measured and implementation levels. The first category is *processes* comprising circular economy: material input, design, production, consumption and end-of-life (EoL) resource management providing input to first phase in a closed loop concept. *Actions* involved are derived from the building blocks for supporting the adoption of circular economy, introduced in Ellen MacArthur Foundation. Circular product design and production includes many methods like eco-design to support re-use, refurbishment and recycling of products or cleaner product and process design. Business models count in new models such as product-service systems or consumer-to-consumer channels enabling collaborative consumption. Cascade/reverse cycle skills are the actions facilitating circular economy such as innovative technologies for recycling or cascaded use of materials. Cross cycle and cross sector collaborations involves the actions to build collaboration both across the value chain and new actors in an industrial symbiosis perspective. *Requirements to be measured* are compiled from EEA report (2016) as reducing input and use of natural resources, reducing emission levels, reducing losses of valuable materials, increasing share of renewable and recyclable resources and increasing the value durability of products. Lastly, it is proposed that all these categories can be applied in three *implementation levels*: the macro level (from cities to nations); the meso level (eco-industrial parks) and the micro level (single companies or customers) [5].

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment			
	Author:	EKODENGE		Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423		Date:	31/8/17

Figure 6 Circular Economy Assessment Framework

Elia et al (2016) summarizes index-based environmental assessment methodologies for measuring the adoption of CE. A classification of these methodologies was made based on two factors: (i) typology of the method (single or multiple indicators), (ii) parameters to be measured (i.e., material flow, energy flow, land use and consumption and other life cycle based) [5].

Table 3 The proposed taxonomy of index-based methodologies (adapted from [5])

The proposed taxonomy of index-based methodologies		
Parameter	Single Indicator	Multiple Indicators
Material Flow	Water Footprint (WF) Material Inputs per Unit of Service (MIPS) Ecological Rucksack (ER)	Material Flow Analysis (MFA) Substance Flow Analysis (SFA)
Energy Flow	Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) Embodied Energy (EE) Emergy Analysis (EMA) Exergy Analysis (EXA)	
Land use and Consumption	Ecological Footprint (EF) Sustainable Process Index (SPI) Dissipation Area Index (DAI)	
Other Life Cycle Based	Carbon Footprint (CF) Ecosystem Damage Potential (EDP)	Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) Environmental Performance Strategy Map (EPMS) Sustainable Environmental Performance Indicator (SEPI)

After assessment of environmental methodologies in terms of circular economy requirements and a detailed review of literature on measuring circular economy through indicators, Elia et al.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE		Version: 1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423		Date: 31/8/17

designed a guideline for measuring the effectiveness of CE quantitatively at the micro level. The suggested guideline is given in *Figure 7*:

- 1) Identify the system to be analyse and the main process(es) to monitor
- 2) Identify the actions to be implemented
- 3) Identify the CE requirements
- 4) Selection of appropriate methodology to assess circularity

Figure 7 Critical steps in the assessment of a CE strategy [5]

Increasing the value durability of products, which is a crucial parameter to measure circular economy, is not included in this study since it is not covered by any of the examined environmental assessment methods. Although Elia et al (2016) reveals a complementary framework for circular economy and a solid methodology for assessing it, this study focuses only on the environmental impacts, missing out environmental and societal impacts. [5]

Jiliang and Chen (2013) developed a unified Circular Economy Index System to assess the whole manufacturing industrial chain. First, manufacturing industrial chain is divided in four parts [20]:

- (i) upper reach industry: mining and raw material production
- (ii) middle reach industry: production of primary products
- (iii) lower reach industry: production of the final products

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

(iv) vein industry: disassembly of products and recovery of wastes

Next, the key indexes and controlling parameters and related indicators for circular economy progress of an industrial chain is defined as given in Table 4. [20]

Table 4 Key indexes and indicators compiled by Jiliang and Chen (2013) [20]

Key indexes and indicators	
Key indexes and controlling parameters	Examples of indicators
Energy saving	Electricity consumption Coal consumption Gas consumption
Material consumption	Raw material consumption Water consumption
Waste disposal and recycle	Waste water Waste gas Solid waste Waste oil
Product and packing material discovery	Old product upgrade Component part reuse Packaging material recovery
Green design	Design for disassemble Design for recovery
Raw material production	Mineral mining Raw material smelting Raw material purchase

Although this is a generic list, that can be adapted to any industrial chain, the weights and function of each item will differ. Therefore, as the next stage, a weight variable model is developed using a combination of *entropy coefficient method* and *partial variable weight method*. Developed CEIS methodology is applied to iron and steel industry and automotive industry [20].

2.5 Life Cycle Approach

Life cycle thinking is an approach to consider the economic, environmental and social impacts of a product (or a project) covering all life cycle steps from “cradle to grave”; starting from the extraction of natural resources to the final disposal of the product along with any material recycling, energy recovery, reuse that may occur prior to ultimate disposition. Within this regard, life cycle assessment is a quantitative application methodology of life cycle thinking in order to evaluate the environmental performance and impacts of a product or a service. Accordingly,

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

LCA is situated as a well-developed framework between all environmental decision making tools.[21]

Specifically, LCA enables decision makers to audit the environmental performance of a product system covering all of the steps related to the life cycle of that product. Moreover, LCA enables to quantify the multiple environmental impacts that address various environmental issues (e.g., climate change) so that the decision maker can understand what trade-offs may need to be made. Lastly, LCA is flexible and can be applied focused on the key questions a decision maker should be considering when evaluating packaging options. [21]

LCA was advanced to provide a new, systematic paradigm to assess the environmental impact of product systems over the whole life cycle, from the production of raw materials (cradle) to the final disposal, covering the impact of landfill and discharges into air and water (grave) that occur with or without partial recycling to a new lifecycle (the next cradle). Considering this way of thinking, modelling a life cycle in this way is complex as all processes of product systems and also the subsystems are very closely interlinked.[22]

Young (2006) states that conventional “Cradle to Grave” approach is replaced by a renewing cycle of “Cradle to Cradle (C2C)” analysis which rebuilds the linear thinking of industrial capitalism model into a closed loop system. Hence, this paradigm enhanced the concept of life cycle thinking and LCA modelling as well. [22]

LCA is one of several environmental management tools with its flexible, applicable and user-friendly modelling design so that LCA can cover not only in environmental issues but also economic (LCC) and even social indicators (S-LCA) as well. Consequently, LCA is a key modelling tool to improve resource efficiency allowing the stakeholders to examine the “hotspots” along the supply chain, as well as the potential risks and opportunities. [23]

Therefore, LCA can assist in [23]:

- Illustrating opportunities of products at certain points of their whole life cycle stages in order to improve the environmental performance
- Supporting the decision-makers in industry, government and non-governmental organizations
- Picking appropriate environmental performance indicators covering the evaluation techniques
- Marketing (e.g., eco-labeling)

Typically, LCA modelling has 4 stages [24][25]:

- Goal and Scope definition
- Inventory analysis
- Life cycle impact assessment
- Life cycle interpretation

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

In an LCA study, “goal” step defines the reasons to conduct the research, intended application and audience. “Scope” identifies the production system to be studied and the related functions of it. Moreover, functional unit, system boundaries, allocation procedures, life cycle impact categories, assumptions and limitations are defined here.

In the “Inventory Analysis” (LCI) phase, data are collected to measure the inputs and outputs of the product system. The results generated after inventory analysis will be further used regarding the potential environmental impacts. After valid and comprehensive data are gathered for each system defined, the impact assessment is carried out.

“Impact Assessment” phase uses the LCI data in order to evaluate the potential environmental impacts, which are already selected in the scope phase. The environmental impact categories are identified by their impact pathway and impact indicator and the elementary flows from the inventory are assigned to the impact categories according to the substances’ ability to contribute to environmental problems. Then, the impact from each emission is modelled quantitatively according to the underlying environmental mechanism.

The final step of an LCA study is the interpretation of results from both LCI and LCIA phases. If needed, a weighting of the environmental impact categories will be performed reflecting the relative importance that they have in the selected project process. One of the most important characteristics of this overall process is that goal and scope of the project, impact assessment methods etc. can change based on the available data at hand. This iterative nature contributes to comprehensiveness and consistency of LCA.[24][25]

Figure 8 General LCA Framework [24][25]

Since LCA study is greatly an iterative process, the LCA expert may need to go back to goal and scope phase after the preliminary inventory work, to move back from impact assessment to inventory analysis, to have a look at the interpretation in an early stage as well [26].

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Life Cycle Costing Assessment (LCC)

Life Cycle Costing (LCC) is a significant economic analysis showing the selection of alternatives that affect both pending and future costs. As conventional cost analysis methods usually do not include environmental costs such as recycling, those may mislead the decision makers into improper investments. LCC analysis clarifies all the costs related to the product life cycle stages with relevant actors as supplier, producer, user/consumer, end-of-life manager etc. [27].

ISO 15686-5 standard identifies life cycle costing as the methodology for systematic economic evaluation of life cycle costs over a period of analysis that may cover the whole life cycle (WLC) of a project or product or some selected life cycle stages. While LCC considers costs only, whole-life costing includes all costs as well as benefits over a period of analysis. During whole life costing (WLC), all significant and reveal initial and future costs and benefits of an asset, throughout its life cycle while fulfilling the performance requirements. In the circular economy point of view, there is a necessity to perform a full analysis on the stages of the value chain including the perspective of the actors. Moreover, "double counting" should be avoided, as the economic gain for one actor could be loss for another [27].

WLC is calculated as net present value (NPV), which is achieved by discounting all expenses during the scope of system to the present. This methodology provides the possibility of comparing different systems and investments where the expenses differ during the calculation period. For the NPV calculations, following formulas are utilized.

Discount rates
$$r = \frac{1+d}{1+i} - 1$$

Where d is the interest rate and i is the inflation rate

Net present value
$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^{t=T} \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t}$$

Where t (0,...,T) is the project or assessment period, C_t is the cash flow occurring in year t, and r is the discount rate.

Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA)

Social life cycle approach is to analyse social, sociological and socio-economic impacts of the products along their life cycle. Social impacts are taken as the consequences of the positive

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

and/or negative pressures on social endpoints (i.e. well-being of stakeholders) [28]. S-LCA aims to promote improvements on overall social (and socioeconomic) conditions throughout the product life cycle.

Social impacts are revealed by consequences of social relations (interactions) placed in the context of an activity (production, consumption or disposal) and/or engendered by it and/or by preventive or reinforcing actions taken by stakeholders (e.g., enforcing safety measures in a facility). Considering the causes of social impacts, this generally implies three dimensions:

Behaviours: social impacts are those caused by a specific behaviour or decision. E.g. forbidding employees to form unions, allowing illegal child labour, and seizing employees' identity papers.

Socio-economic processes: social impacts are the closely related effects of socio-economic decisions. E.g. an investment decision in a sector to build infrastructure in a community.

Capitals (human, social, cultural): social impacts related on the ground of an individual, a group, a society (e.g., systemic poverty). They can be either positive or negative.

Social impacts are often perceived as being very complex. Actually, they are the result of relationships carrying a set of different angles. Social impacts are function of many factors: politic, economy, ethics, psychology, legal issues, culture, etc. Moreover, social impacts feed back to the production system and the society and therefore change other social and environmental impacts. As of this complexity and this subjectivity, it is not recommended to define attributes of relationships unilaterally and from there define a set of related indicators isolated from the stakeholder context. As for environmental impacts, defining social impact categories needs to go through a subjective and inter-subjective process, preferably at the international level [28].

In order to assess both positive and negative impacts of "social", in other words "sociological", aspects and the related potential along the product value chain, S-LCA is a reliable, up-to-date and applicable method. Considering the sustainability, especially from a business perspective, involvement of social aspects is somehow marginal as compared to the other two dimensions [29]. However, stakeholders demand the inclusion of social sustainability as well as the environmental and economic concerns. Although the social dimension is generally assumed as the "weakest" pillar of the sustainability, there exist definite evaluations via social sustainability indicators in the process of business evolution. Accordingly, S-LCA methodology proposes an evaluation of social impact indicators by addressing "what social criteria should be assessed?" and "how those criteria should be assessed" [30].

Stakeholders, subcategory indicators and related inventory indicators will be covered in section 3.6

2.6 Life Cycle Approach for the Assessment of Value Chains

Considering circular economy concept on value chain of a product, Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) appears to be an effective tool in order to add significant value on the product supply chain.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment	
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version: 1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date: 31/8/17

LCA tool was advanced under the principles and guidelines established by ISO standards [24][25]. In general, the CE aims to sustain valuable materials via a set of feedback loops between the life cycle phases of the product regarding resource efficient industrial processes [31]. Accordingly, LCA is an applicable tool to analyse the environmental aspects of complex product systems [32], covering recycling and circular schemes [33]. LCA measures the environmental performance of a product or service by spotting out the critical stages in a supply chain in which emissions should be reduced [32]. As a result, LCA allows decision makers to pick up the feasible option among diverse impact categories and those can be documented when analysing different solutions for more environmentally friendly systems [34].

Figure 9 Sustainable Circular Economy Supply Chain Approach [1]

One key feature of LCA is that this approach allows companies to move away from just handling their own operations to see what is happening in their value chain (upstream and downstream operations) [21]. Considering the food packaging, while a large industry in its own right, it is only one of the many stakeholders in the larger industry. Industry players will need to work together to ensure that food is not only efficiently grown and harvested, but also distributed and accessible for consumption. Solutions will span the whole value chain, from increasing field productivity to building necessary infrastructure for transportation and storage. Hence, LCA appears to be a

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

necessary tool for both packaging designers and others who involved in the packaging value chain, e.g. governments and others involved in policy management [23]. By applying LCA, more generally life cycle approach, to assess the value chain of the product system, decision makers can make more clear choices and also ensure those choices lead to improved environmental performance of packaging. It is important to adapt those practices to “make a system”, to fit together along value chains functioning in loops, closed or not (including design, production consumption, and the return to the biosphere or the reuse) to generate a more sustainable development model [35].

3 SUSTAINABILITY AND CIRCULARITY INDICATORS

3.1 General Properties of the Indicators

3.1.1 SMART Criteria

Indicators illustrate change of direction or “a signpost of change” in performance or state of a system depending on time-bound data over a given period of time [36] [37]. Above all, indicators may help to:

- Measure progress and achievements;
- Clarify consistency between activities, outputs, outcomes and goals;
- Ensure legitimacy and accountability to all stakeholders by demonstrating progress;
- Assess project and staff performance [36].

There are certain properties proposed for an indicator, which can be either a basic indicator or a composite one, to help its purpose of reflecting the domain it is targeted. These so-called indicator criteria are generally abbreviated by taking the first letters of the indicator properties they cover.

“SMART” is the first of those criteria, which states that the indicators should be **S**pecific, **M**easurable, **A**ttainable, **R**elevant, and **T**ime-bound. In particular:

Specific: Indicators must address clearly the claimed result when measuring without interfering with other factors.

- Is it clear exactly what is being measured? Has the appropriate level of disaggregation been specified?
- Does the indicator capture the essence of the desired result?
- Does it capture differences across areas and categories of people?
- Is the indicator specific enough to measure progress towards the result?

Measurable: Indicators must be precisely defined in order to have explicit measurement. This generally means quantitative (percentage, ratio, number), but qualitative as well.

- Are changes objectively verifiable?
- Will the indicator show desirable change?
- Is it a reliable and clear measure of results?
- Is it sensitive to changes in policies and programmes?

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

- Do stakeholders agree on exactly what to measure?

Attainable: The necessary data must be measured and collected.

- What changes are anticipated as a result of the assistance?
- Are the result(s) realistic? For this, a credible link between outputs, contributions of partnerships and outcome is indispensable.

Relevant: The indicators must provide appropriate information for the programme/project objectives and support guide decisions that key users will need to make.

- Does the indicator capture the essence of the desired result?
- Is it relevant to the intended outputs and outcome?
- Is the indicator plausibly associated with the sphere of activity?

Time-bound: Indicators should clearly address the change when it is expected. An indicator is required to be collected and reported on time.

- Are data actually available at reasonable cost and effort?
- Are data sources known?
- Does an indicator monitoring plan exist? [36] [37].

Furthermore, another recent acronym is “SPICED”; **S**ubjective, **P**articipatory, **I**nterpreted, **C**ommunicable, **E**mpowering and **D**isaggregated. SMART describes the properties of the indicators concerning how they should be used. The SPICED approach allows the stakeholders to define and use the indicator for their own purposes on interpreting and learning about the change, rather than simply measuring or attempting to demonstrate impact to meet requirements [38].

3.1.2 RACER Criteria

The EC's Impact Assessment Guidelines specify the widely accepted RACER criteria for useful indicators. It is an evaluation framework developed for assessing the value of scientific tools to be used in policy making. RACER is an acronym to state:

- **R**elevant = closely linked to the objectives to be reached
- **A**ccepted = by staff, stakeholders, and other users
- **C**redible = accessible to non-experts, unambiguous and easy to interpret
- **E**asy = feasible to monitor and collect data at a reasonable cost
- **R**obust = not easily manipulated [39].

The RACER Criteria is explained in Figure 10.[39]

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Figure 10 RACER Criteria explained [43]

3.2 Sustainability Indicator Sets

3.2.1 UN Sustainable Development Goals Indicators

On the 1st of January 2016, the 17 SDGs with 169 targets of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development officially came into force. The SDGs and targets are integrated and indivisible, global in nature and universally applicable, considering different national realities, capacities and levels of development and respecting national policies and priorities. Targets are defined as inspirational and global so one government can set its own national targets in accordance with them. Perceiving the link between sustainable development and other relevant ongoing processes in the economic, social and environmental fields is highly necessary.[40]

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE		Version: 1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423		Date: 31/8/17

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

Figure 11 Sustainable Development Goals [41]

Within this regard, the 17 SDGs are as follows:

- Goal 1. End poverty in all its forms everywhere
- Goal 2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture
- Goal 3. Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages
- Goal 4. Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all
- Goal 5. Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls
- Goal 6. Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all
- Goal 7. Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all
- Goal 8. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all
- Goal 9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation
- Goal 10. Reduce inequality within and among countries
- Goal 11. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable
- Goal 12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns
- Goal 13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts*
- Goal 14. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development
- Goal 15. Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

- Goal 16. Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels
- Goal 17. Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development

The following global indicator framework was developed by the Inter-Agency and Expert Group on SDG Indicators and agreed to, as a practical starting point at the 47th session of the UN Statistical Commission held in March 2016. The global indicator list is contained in the *Report of the Inter-Agency and Expert Group on Sustainable Development Goal Indicators (E/CN.3/2016/2/Rev.1), Annex IV* and provided below.[42]

The list includes 230 indicators on which general agreement has been reached. The indicator list referenced above is open-source and quite long to be placed in this section so that only the relevant indicators or the indicator sets are decided to be stated below regarding the CIRC-PACK targets[42];

Table 5 SDG Indicators Related to the CIRC-PACK Project

SDG Indicators Related to the CIRC-PACK Project			
CIRC-PACK Objectives	Related SDG	Goals and Targets	Indicators
"In order to enhance the existing "plastic economy", DC-C builds a multi-sectorial interaction boosting new economies based on plastic recycling."	Goal 8. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all	8.4 Improve progressively, through 2030, global resource efficiency in consumption and production and endeavour to decouple economic growth from environmental degradation, in accordance with the 10-Year Framework of Programmes on Sustainable Consumption and Production, with developed countries taking the lead	8.4.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP (Gross Domestic Product)
	Goal 12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns	12.2 By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources	12.2.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP
		12.5 By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse	12.5.1 National recycling rate, tons of material recycled

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

"Improving plastic value chain in terms of circular economy and encourage industrial symbiosis."	Goal 9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation	9.4 By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities	9.4.1 CO ₂ emission per unit of value added
"New bio-based products, as well as new recycling channels will be developed along with reducing the impact of leakages by means of new biodegradable plastics."	Goal 14. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development	14.1 By 2025, prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution of all kinds, in particular from land-based activities, including marine debris and nutrient pollution	14.1.1 Index of coastal eutrophication and floating plastic debris density
"the application of CIRC-PACK solutions will create a number of new jobs estimated as 60 per kton of biobased plastic produced, around 100 per AHP recovery plant developed, and other DC related new jobs that will be further investigated during the project"	· Goal 9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation	9.2 Promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and, by 2030, significantly raise industry's share of employment and gross domestic product, in line with national circumstances, and double its share in least developed countries	9.2.2 Manufacturing employment as a proportion of total employment
"the effective promotion of gender equality and the gender dimension in research and innovation content under Horizon 2020"	Goal 5. Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls	5.5 Ensure women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and public life	5.5.2 Proportion of women in managerial positions

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

3.2.2 UNEP Sustainable Consumption and Production Headline Indicators

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) is the prominent global environmental authority that sets the global environmental agenda, promotes the consistent operations of the environmental dimension of sustainable development. UNEP placed in United Nations system and serves as an authoritative advocate for the global environment. UNEP's Sustainable Consumption and Production indicators (SCP) aim to monitor the interface between the economy, environment and society; the resource use and waste flows due to the consumption and production activities. These indicators provide information on whether and at what rate progress is being made towards SCP patterns and additionally they are organized into six domains including (1) scale of resource use, (2) decoupling, (3) environmental impact, (4) technology and lifestyles, (5) financing and investing for SCP, and (6) policy support for SCP [44].

SCP indicators clarify the following with respect to the broader topic of sustainable consumption and production:

1. *Resource and critical thresholds/carrying capacity:* Some SCP indicators illustrate the levels and trends associated with stresses on critical ecosystems and processes occurring within, which may contribute to overflow of critical thresholds and carrying capacity. Although it may be difficult to determine the critical thresholds and carrying capacity, the information provided by SCP indicators on this matter provides early warning for decision-makers and public which impacts the policy making process.
2. *Decoupling:* One of the important aspects of the sustainable consumption and production is the requirement to decouple economic growth from resource use and environmental degradation. Decoupling, claimed as a policy goal, can include disconnection of economic growth from resource use or environmental impacts. The relationship between economic activities with the level of primary resource use is referred by resource decoupling. On the other hand, impact decoupling, evaluated by state or impact indicators, relates to the relationship between economic activities and their environmental impacts.
3. *Social benefits:* Indicators under this theme try to quantify how SCP contributes to better access of society to higher quality and sustainable goods and services while reducing the environmental footprint of consumption, therefore social benefits of SCP activities.
4. *Universality:* Sustainability in consumption and production is applicable to all countries globally without taking their level of development into account. In developed countries, it implies shifting towards more resource- and energy-efficient/circular economies with less (or even zero) waste and emissions, adopting sustainable lifestyles and reducing unnecessary consumption. In developing countries on the other hand, the concept goes along with the opportunities for setting up sustainability through more resource efficiency, environmentally sound and competitive practices and technologies. Accordingly, the development status of different countries may dictate different priorities during assessments utilizing SCP indicators.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

5. *Linkages to other targets:* SCP, which is a crosscutting issue, can be addressed directly or indirectly (by focusing on energy, water etc.). Therefore, as indicators are selected for some targets, the information can be used to monitor additional targets as well.

SCP indicators consider environmental, economic and social concerns by taking both supply and demand side of the market, bringing a holistic view to assess sustainability as a result. On the production side, SCP refers to the set of cleaner production practices and eco-efficiency of production systems. On the consumption side, it refers to the shift in consumer behaviour towards more sustainable practices in order to reduce environmental footprints.

Table 6 UNEP SCP Headline Indicators [44]

UNEP SCP Headline Indicators	
Domain	Indicators
Scale of resource use	Domestic Material Consumption - DMC (tonnes, tonnes/capita, tonnes/GDP)
	Material footprint* (tonnes, tonnes/capita, tonnes/GDP)
Decoupling economic activity from resource use and environmental impact	National material efficiency – material productivity (GDP per unit material use) Production side: Material used measured through DMC Consumption side: Material used measured through material footprint
	National energy efficiency – Energy productivity (GDP per unit of energy use)
Impacts	Contaminants in air, water and soil from industrial sources, agriculture, transport and water/wastewater treatment plants (kg of contaminants)
	Number of persons killed or injured by a natural and technological disaster and economic losses
	Ocean health – Ocean Health Index
Technology and lifestyles	Sectorial material and energy efficiency
	Market share of goods and services certified by sustainability labelling schemes
Financing and investing to transform the economy to SCP	Amount of R&D spending on environmentally sound technologies
	Amount of fossil fuel subsidies, per unit of GDP (production and consumption), and as proportion of total national expenditure on fossil fuels
Policy support for SCP	Number of countries with SCP National Action Plans or SCP mainstreamed as priority
	Number of countries with inter-ministerial coordination and multi-stakeholder mechanisms supporting SCP

* Also referred as raw material consumption [45][44]

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

3.2.3 European Benchmark Indicators

The Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency has developed The European Benchmark Indicators (EBI) in order to compare the Member State's environmental performances. They consider both economic and social setting of a country as well as their environmental performance since the environment can be very different because of differences in e.g. demography and economic structure [46].

The EBI have two branches; first on socioeconomic profile, that should put environmental performance into proper perspective and second on the environmental profile built upon the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's (OECD) DPSIR (Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response) framework. If possible, socioeconomic indicators include data on the present situation and trends from the past. The environmental indicators are measures in accordance with environmental pressures and include existing aggregated indicators such as Ecological Footprint [46]. Composite indicators help to assess the overall ranking of the country among other Member States. Although is a Nation level set of indicators, not applicable to CIRC-PACK, it is relevant in a sustainable indicator revision and could be used as the basis to develop a set of more global indicators.

Table 7 European Benchmark Indicators (EBI) [46]

The European Benchmark Indicators			
Socio-economic Profile		Environmental profile	
Economic Performance	Economic structure	Biodiversity	Air quality
Welfare	Economy Openness	Pressures	Pressures
Labour Productivity	Sector Structure	Built-up Area	Road Transp. NOx Emiss.
Annual Working Hours	Energy Structure	Land Fragmentation	Road Transp. SO2 Emiss.
Income Distribution	Transport Str. Freight	Ammonia Emissions	Road Transp. Ozone Emiss.
R&D Intensity	Transport Str. Passeng.	Quality	Technology
Growth Comp. Index	Energy Intensity Economy	Threatened Mammals	Catalytic Converters
Socio-economic drivers	Energy Supply Security	Protected Areas	Diesel Cars
Population Size	Direct Material Productivity	Policy Performance	Age Passenger Cars
Population Density	Human capital	Habitat Directive	Industry Pollution, SO2
Household Size	Education Expenditure	Birds Directive	Industry Pollution, NOx
Livestock Density	Unemployment	Habitat Sufficiency Index	Industry Pollution, PM10
Cars per km2	Education	Ammonia NEC Target	Quality

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	Qualifications		
Cars per population	Health - HALE	Water quality	Urban - PM10
Tourism Expenditure	Health - Expenditure	<i>Pressures</i>	Urban - Ozone
Direct Material Input	Ageing Society	Fertilizer Consumption	Rural - PM10
Fuel prices and taxes	Health Risk - Obesity	Pesticides Sales	Rural - Ozone
Diesel Price	Law and public opinion	Nitrogen Balance	Premature Deaths
Petrol Price	Public Policy Priority	Organic Manure	<i>Policy Performance</i>
Electricity Price Households	Public Env. Policy Priority	<i>Technology</i>	Ozone NEC Target
Electricity Price Industry	EU Infringement Cases	Organic Farming	Climate change
VAT Rate Electricity	EU Confidence Index	Wastewater Treatment	<i>Pressures</i>
Gas Price Households	EU Council Country Votes	<i>Quality</i>	CO ₂ Emissions per capita
Gas Price Industry		Rivers Nitrate	GHG Emissions per capita
		Rivers Phosphorus	<i>Technology</i>
		Lakes Nitrate	Electricity from Renewables
		Lakes Phosphorus	Energy Efficiency Industry
		Groundwater Nitrate	Heat & Power Generation
		<i>Policy Performance</i>	<i>Policy Performance</i>
		Organic Nitrate Target	GHG Kyoto Target
		Waste	Government & Enterprise
		<i>Pressures</i>	<i>Government</i>
		Municipal Waste	Environmental Tax Revenues
		Packaging Consumption	Public Env-Expenditures
		<i>Technology</i>	Public Env. R&D Expenditures
		Waste Landfilled	<i>Enterprise</i>
		<i>Policy Performance</i>	Business Env-Expenditures
		Recycling Rate Packaging	Eco-management Companies

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

		Natural Resources	Export of Green Products
		<i>Pressures</i>	<i>Policy Performance</i>
		Meat Consumption	EU Env-Infringement cases
		Fish Consumption	
		Paper Consumption	
		Final Energy Cons. H.holds	
		Elect. Cons. H.holds	
		Consumption Gas & Diesel	
		Ecological Footprint	

3.2.4 Sustainable Development Indicators

In order to support policymaking and evaluation at certain stages from problem recognition to policy formulation, decision making and monitoring implementation, The European Commission uses a range of indicators [47]. New indicators are developed and existing indicators are updated whenever necessary in order to supply proper information on key environmental, economic and social issues during the policy-making process. Sustainable Development Strategy (SDS) is one of the important drivers for the utilization of sustainability indicators, which requires the Commission to develop indicators at the appropriate level of detail to monitor outcomes of the sustainability efforts.

Sustainable Development Indicators (SDIs) are advanced by Eurostat in terms of a “hierarchical theme framework” referring the seven key challenges of the European SDS as well as the key objective of economic prosperity, and guiding principles related to good governance. The thematic framework includes ten themes including;

- socioeconomic development,
- sustainable consumption and production,
- social inclusion,
- demographic changes,
- public health,
- climate change and energy,
- sustainable transport,
- natural resources,
- global partnership,
- good governance [48].

In order to refer the operational objectives and actions of the SDS, indicators are further divided into sub-themes [47]. List of SDIs can be found in Table 8.

The indicators are also produced as a three-level pyramid (Figure 12) providing information on overall and operational objectives in addition to actions. The term “contextual indicators” states

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

another group of indicators, which complement the indicators at these three levels and basically provide background information [47] [48]. At the first level of the pyramid, the indicators monitor the overall objectives of the SDS with high robustness and data availability. These so-called headline indicators have the highest communication value. Second level indicators correspond to the sub-themes of the framework such as end-use energy efficiency and savings or integration of adaptation to and mitigation of climate change into policies. At the third level of pyramid, the indicators are associated with the field of sustainable consumption and production [49]. Eurostat indicators at this level are reported to be inadequate to monitor the EU's progress though. A serious gap in framework programme funded research regarding these indicators exist. Specifically, the need for absolute resource use and not just resource efficiency is underlined [47].

Figure 12 Indicator pyramid of the EU SDI framework [48] [49]

Table 8 Eurostat SDIs [48]

Eurostat SDIs	
Evaluation of changes in the socioeconomic development	Sustainable consumption and production
Real GDP per capita *	Resource productivity *
Economic development	Resource use and waste
Investment	Domestic material consumption
Disposal household income	Generation of waste excluding major mineral wastes
Household saving	Hazardous waste generation
Innovativeness, competitiveness and eco-	Recycled and composted municipal waste

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

efficiency	
Labour productivity	Atmospheric emissions
Eco-innovation	Consumption patterns
Research and development expenditure	Electricity consumption of households
Energy intensity	Final energy consumption
Employment	Production patterns
Employment	Environmental management systems
Young people neither in employment or in education or training	Organic farming
Unemployment	
People at risk of poverty or social exclusion *	Employment rate of older workers *
Monetary poverty and living conditions	Demography
Risk of poverty after social transfers	Life expectancy and healthy life years at age 65
Severe material deprivation	Population growth
Income inequalities	Total fertility rate
Access to labour market	Migration
Very low work intensity	Old-age dependency
Working poor	Old age income adequacy
Long-term unemployment	Income level of over 65s compared to before
Gender pay gap	Public finance sustainability
Education	Government debt
Early leavers from education and training	Retirement
Tertiary education	The impact of ageing public expenditure
Lifelong learning	Pension expenditure projections
Education expenditure	
Life expectancy and healthy life years *	Greenhouse gas emissions *
Health and health inequalities	Primary energy consumption *
Deaths due to chronic diseases	Climate change
Unmet needs for medical health care	Greenhouse gas emissions by sector
Long-standing illnesses or health problems	Global surface average temperature
Determinants of health	Greenhouse gas emissions intensity of energy consumption
Production of toxic chemicals	Energy
Exposure to air pollution by particulate matter	Energy dependence
Exposure to air pollution by ozone	Consumption of renewables
Annoyance by noise	Electricity generation from renewables
	Share of renewable energy in transport

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Energy consumption of transport relative to GDP *	Common bird index *
Transport and mobility	Biodiversity
Modal split of freight transport	Protected areas
Volume of freight transport relative to GDP	Fresh water resources
Modal split of passenger transport	Water abstraction
Volume of passenger transport relative to GDP	Water quality in rivers
Transport impacts	Marine ecosystems
Greenhouse gas emissions from transport	Fishing capacity
People killed in road accidents	Land use
Average CO ₂ emissions per kilometer from new passenger cars	Artificial areas
Emissions of ozone precursors from transport	Nutrient balance on agricultural land
Emissions of particulate matter from transport	
Official development assistance (ODA) *	
Globalisation trade	Policy coherence and effectiveness
Imports from developing countries	Citizens' confidence in EU institutions
Imports from least-developed countries	Infringement cases
Subsidies for EU agriculture	Transposition deficit of EU law
Financing of sustainable development	Openness and participation
Financing for developing countries	Voter turnout
Share of foreign direct investment in low-income countries	Citizens' online interaction with public authorities
Share of untied assistance	Economic instruments
Bilateral official development assistance	Environmental taxes compared with labour taxes
Global poverty	
Global resource management	
CO ₂ emissions per inhabitant	
Access to water	

* Headline indicators

3.2.5 Indicators used for the Environmental Policy Review

In order to monitor recent environmental trends and policy development at EU and national level and progress towards the EU's key environmental goals, annual Environmental Policy Review (EPR) is designed [50]. In the year 2009, the report stated 37 indicators that reflect different component under DPSIR framework Table 9. These indicators are classified into six environmental themes that are namely; (1) climate change and energy, (2) nature and biodiversity, (3) environment and health, (4) natural resources and waste, (5) environment and economy, and (6) implementation [51].

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Table 9 Indicators used for the 2009 EPR [51]

Indicators used for the 2009 EPR	
Indicator	DPSIR
Climate Change and Energy	
Global air temperature change	S
Concentration of CO ₂ in the atmosphere	P
Natural disasters linked to climate change	I
Total Kyoto greenhouse gas emissions	P
Share of energy produced from renewable energy sources in final energy consumption	R
Electricity produced from renewable energy sources	R
Combined heat and power generation	R
Energy intensity	R
Final energy consumption by transport	D
Average CO ₂ emissions from passenger cars	D
Cumulative spent fuel from nuclear power plants	D
Nature and biodiversity	
Common birds	S
Conservation status of habitats by habitat group	S
Conservation status of species by taxonomic group	S
Landscape fragmentation	P
Topsoil organic carbon content	S
Freight transport	D
Area occupied by organic farm	R
Area under agri-environmental commitment	R
Natura 2000 area (% terrestrial area)	R
Environment and health	
Urban population exposure to air pollution by particles	S
Urban population exposure to air pollution by ozone	S
Transport noise in urban agglomerations	P
Emission projections for air pollutants	P
Air emissions of nitrogen oxides	P
Water exploitation index	P
Production of toxic chemicals	P
Production of environmentally harmful chemicals	P
Pesticides residues in food	P
Natural resources and waste	
Fish catches from stocks outside safe biological units	S
Total waste generated	P
Municipal waste generated	P
Recycling of packaging waste	R

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Environment and economy	
Environmental taxes	R
Green jobs	R
Net electricity generating installations in EU	R
Implementation	
Infringements of EU environmental legislation	Performance indicator

D: Driving force, P: Pressure, S: State, I: Impact, R: Response

3.2.6 European Environment Agency Core Indicator Set

European Environment Agency (EEA) has developed the core indicator set in accordance with the DPSIR assessment framework. The goal of this set of indicators is to improve the quality and coverage of data flows so that comparability and certainty of information and the assessments achieved with this information is enhanced. Moreover, with the core indicator set, contributions to other indicator initiatives in Europe are streamlined. EEA also aims to implement a manageable and stable ground for indicator based assessments to monitor the progress in priority environmental policy areas [52][53]. The indicator within the core set are classified as

- o Descriptive indicators,
- o Performance indicators,
- o Eco-efficiency indicators,
- o Policy effectiveness indicators, and
- o Total welfare indicators.

Table 10 EEA core indicator set [52][53]

EEA core indicator set					
Indicator	EEA class	DPSIR	Indicator	EEA class	DPSIR
Air pollution indicators					
Emission of acidifying substances	B	P	NO _x emissions	B	P
Emissions of ozone precursors	B	P	NH ₃ emissions	B	P
Emissions of primary PM and secondary PM precursors	B	P	NM VOC emissions	B	P
Exceedance of air quality limit values in urban areas	A	S	Heavy metal emissions	B	P
Exposure of ecosystems to acidification, eutrophication and ozone	B	S	POP emissions	B	P
SO ₂ emissions	B	P			
Biodiversity indicators					
Climate indicators					
Production and consumption of ozone depleting substances	D	D	Greenhouse gas emission trends	B	P
Progress to greenhouse gas emission targets	A	P	Global and European temperature	A	P

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations	A	S	<i>Other indicators not specified</i>		
Energy indicators					
Final energy consumption by sector	A	D	Total primary energy intensity	B	R
Primary energy consumption by fuel	A	D	Renewable electricity consumption	B	R
Renewable primary energy consumption	B	R	Efficiency of conventional thermal electricity generation	C	D
Final energy consumption intensity	A	D	Share of renewable energy in final energy consumption	C	I
Overview of the European energy system	C	D	Progress on energy efficiency in EU	C	R
Overview of the electricity production and use in EU	C	D			
Water indicators					
Use of freshwater resources	A	P	Oxygen consuming substances in rivers	A	S
Nutrients in freshwater	A	S	Nutrients in transitional, coastal and marine waters	A	S
Bathing water quality	A	S	Chlorophyll in transitional, coastal and marine waters	A	S
Urban wastewater treatment	A	R	Hazardous substances in marine organisms	A	P
Emission intensity of agriculture in Europe	C	P	Emission intensity of domestic sector in Europe	C	P
Emission intensity of manufacturing industry in EU	C	P			
Waste and resources					
Waste generation		P	Waste recycling		R
Diversion of waste from landfill		R	Total primary energy intensity		R
Decoupling of resource use from environmental pressures		D	Decoupling of resource use from environmental impacts		D

- o D: Driving force, P: Pressure, S: State, I: Impact, R: Response
- o A: descriptive indicator, B: performance indicator, C: eco-efficiency indicator, D: policy effectiveness indicator, E: total welfare indicator

3.2.7 Ecosystem-based Indices for Industries

This sub-section's goal is to monitor the ecosystem assessment methods developed in the last years that are applicable for a process and product oriented approach.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Table 11 Ecosystem-Based Indices for Industries

Ecosystem-Based Indices for Industries				
Name	No. of sub-indicators	Scaling/normalisation	Weighting	Aggregation
Material Input Per unit of Service (MIPS)	5 categories	MI factors	Equal	-
Sustainability Performance Index	5	Area	Equal	Total area per unit product divided by area per capita
Ecological Footprint	6	Area	Equal	Summation
Sustainable Environmental Performance Indicator	5	Area (deviation-from-target methodology)	Equal	Radar diagram
Eco-compass	6	Indices are expressed in monetary terms	Different weighting vectors	-
Environment assessment for cleaner production	5 "profiles"	Mathematical formula for each indicator	Equal	Square root of the sum of squares of profile indices
COMPLIMENT	5 categories	Life Cycle Impact Assessment	AHP	Weighted sum

Material Input Per unit of Service (MIPS)

MIPS is a measure developed at the Wuppertal Institute stands for Material Input per Service unit, MIPS, as a targeted and practicable indicator, helps to illustrate the positive as well as the financial potential of a resource-conserving entrepreneurship (use and service management, cost and resource efficiency). MIPS evaluates the use of resources from the point of their extraction from nature: all data which meet the amount of moved tons in nature, hence meet the categories of biotic or renewable raw material, abiotic or non-renewable raw material, water, air and earth movement in agriculture and silviculture (incl. erosion).

Sustainability Performance Index (SPI)

The Sustainability Performance Index is formed on an operationalized form of the principle of sustainability. It uses only process data known at an early stage of planning and data of natural concentrations of substances (not on their presumable impact, which is usually not known). The evaluation of the area needed to embed a process completely into the biosphere is the core of the SPI evaluation [54]. This comprises the area required for production of raw material, process energy and provided installations as well as the area required for the staff and for the accumulation of products and by-products within the available area [55].

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Ecological Footprint (EF)

The ecological footprint (EF) is based on the quantitative land and water requirements to sustain a (national) living standard into infinity thereby assuming certain efficiency improvements [56]. The ratio of necessary resources to available resources is interpreted as a measure of ecological sustainability: ratios exceeding one are seen as unsustainable, i.e. contemporary living standards would violate the principles of sustainable development. Evaluation of the EF is based on data from national consumption statistics. Therefore, the EF primarily relies on normalization (as any consumption is converted in land use). Weighting is rather implicit in the conversion parameter and aggregation is done by summing up all land and water requirements. There are several approaches similar to the EF, e.g. the MIPS (Material-Input-Per-Service) concept or the Ecoindex™ [57] [58] [59].

Sustainable Environmental Performance Indicator (SEPI)

The Sustainable Environmental Performance Indicator (SEPI) has been suggested recently, and it is designed to contain any combination of quantitative indicators, although it is currently depicted as a combination of different footprints. De Benedetto and Klemeš (2009a&b) describes the SEPI indicator and an approach that complements environmental, financial and other considerations in detail by [60][61].

The limited inclusion of cost and investment considerations significantly restricts the applicability of LCA as a source of input for strategic decision-making. As a result, the Environmental Performance Strategy Map (EPSM) was developed. The EPSM blends financial, environmental, resource, and toxicological considerations into a single analysis. It considers environmental and social footprints. Furthermore, cost is considered in an additional category that relates to all of the other categories. EPSM aims to provide a single indicator for each option. The best option from the environmental or social and financial perspectives can subsequently be selected based on this approach. A deviation-from-target methodology is used, in which a maximum target is defined for each of the footprints, and each value is expressed as a percentage of the distance to that target. The normalized values of the footprints are mapped on a spider diagram. The cost is taken as an additional dimension as it is not used for comparative reasons. The volume of each pyramid represents the overall environmental or social and financial impact of the option under consideration. This indicator is termed the SEPI. The EPSM enables the comparison of different footprints based on a single SEPI.

EPSM combines the main indicators with the SEPI as a single measurement for the sustainability of a given option. Despite, the weaknesses are also, amongst others, the limited availability and uncertainty of data, time intensiveness to perform the study, and highly possible errors relating to the conversion of emissions to an area unit.

Eco-compass

Dow Chemical has developed the Eco-compass to provide a simple, visual summary of LCA data [62]. It is due to the indicators of eco-efficiency developed by the World Business Council

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), with some minor amendments [63]. The Eco-compass has six 'poles' or dimensions:

- energy intensity
- mass intensity
- health and environmental potential risk
- resource conservation
- extent of re-valorization (re-use, re-manufacturing and re-cycling)
- service extension.

Environment Assessment for Cleaner Production Technologies

An environmental assessment method was developed by Fijal (2007) for cleaner production technologies enabling quantitative analysis of environmental impact [64]. The method is due to material and energy flows and uses a set of profile indices, including raw material, energy, waste, product and packaging profiles that describe all material and energy flows related to the technology under investigation. The indices are used as a basis for determining an integrated index for overall environmental assessment of cleaner production technologies. In order to evaluate environmental nuisance of implemented, modernized and modified technological processes and products the presented method can be employed to perform comparative analyses of alternative technologies.

COMPLIMENT—Environment Performance Index for Industries

COMPLIMENT by Hermann et al. (2007) was developed as an analytical tool which can be used to provide detailed information on the overall environmental impact of a business [65]. COMPLIMENT integrates parts of tools such as life cycle assessment, multi-criteria analysis and environmental performance indicators. The methodology is based on environmental performance indicators, expanding the scope of data collection towards a life cycle approach and covering a weighting and aggregation step. In the method; EPIs are calculated at the beginning while the goal and scope definition of an LCA were considered, followed by data collection, analysis and conversion and subsequently the classification, characterisation and normalisation steps. Performing classification, characterisation and normalisation result in a set of output data in the form of impact categories, such as global warming, acidification potential, eutrophication potential, ozone precursors and human health. Three sets of weights based on local, regional and national perspectives were developed by using AHP analysis. In the next phase of COMPLIMENT, the weights per impact category are multiplied by the normalized potential impacts per category. The resulting weighted impacts per category can then be added up to form an index of the normalized total potential environmental impact for each perspective.

3.2.8 Composite Indices for Industries

Composite indicators are an innovative approach to evaluating sustainable development and resource efficiency. There were numerous attempts in literature to move beyond the non-integrated and combine different nature-society dimensions in a single evaluation methodology. Firstly the three aspects of sustainable development were faced through the

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

development of methodological framework, with relatively simple, informative and easily available indicators.

Nevertheless, aggregation was not considered in the above-mentioned methodologies. Computing aggregate values is a common method used for constructing indices. An index can be either simple or weighted depending on its purpose. Such an approach allows for the evaluation of a multitude of aspects, which can then be deciphered into a single comparable index.

The construction of composite indicators involves making choices, with issues of uncertainty such as selection of data, imprecision of data, data imputation methods, data normalization, weighting schemes, weights values and aggregation methods. This sub-sections aims to review the most relevant methodologies within this field.

Table 12 Composite Indices for Industries

Composite Indices for Industries				
Name	Nr. of sub-indicators	Scaling/normalisation	Weighting	Aggregation
Composite Sustainable Development index	Three categories; 38 indicators	Distance from maximum and minimum	AHP	Weighted average
Composite Sustainability Performance Index	Five categories; 59 indicators	Distance from mean divided by standard deviation	AHP	Weighted average
ITT Flygt sustainability index	40	[+10, -100]	Company opinion	Summation
G score	5 categories	Subjective	Equal	Summation
Methodological approach of Politecnico di Milano	NA	NA	NA	NA

Composite Sustainable Development Index

Krajnc and Glavic (2005) collected and developed a standardized set of sustainability indicators for companies covering all main aspects of sustainable development [66]. A composite sustainable development index (ICSD) in order to track integrated information on economic, environmental, and social performance of the company with time. Normalised indicators were associated into three sustainability sub-indices and finally composed into an overall indicator of a company performance. This was applied by determining the impact of individual indicator to the overall sustainability of a company using the concept of analytic hierarchy process.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Composite Sustainability Performance Index (CSPI)

The composite sustainability performance index (CSPI) is an attempt to develop a measure of corporate citizenship and to critically evaluate how well a company stands up to its policies and commitments regarding sustainable development. This model enables industry to identify the key sustainability performance indicators and provides framework for aggregating the various indicators into the CSPI [67]. The calculation of CSPI is a step-by-step procedure of grouping various basic indicators into the sustainability sub-index for each group of sustainability indicators. Sub-indices then subsequently derived in the form of aggregated index. Weights are derived using AHP methodology. Liberator scoring and Z score method were employed for aggregation of indicators. The model has been evaluated based on the real-time application for a steel industry. CSPI with its sub-indices for each dimensions of sustainability were evaluated for the time period of 4 years.

ITT Flygt Sustainability Index

ITT Flygt Sustainability Index suggests a method for measurement of corporate contribution to sustainable development, looking at how well a company stands up to its policies and commitments regarding sustainable development. This index is developed and calculated for ITT Flygt AB over a 3 years period (2002–2004). The index structure is based on scientific literature and interviews with ITT Flygt and four other engineering companies. The purpose of the index is to support corporate sustainability-management. The index is calculated by aggregating some 40 sustainability-indicators. These indicators are individual to each company and are designed to measure the significant sustainability aspects of the company [68].

G Score Method

“G score” consists of five categories, namely general environmental management (GEM), input, process, output, and outcome. G score is a proxy measure of corporate environmental performance based on voluntary environment, health, and safety (EHS) report and is calculated by aggregating the points of the above five-categories [69].

Development of a methodological approach and application to the iron and steel sector. The document “Come Misurare la Sostenibilità: Sviluppo di un Approccio Metodologico e Applicazione al Settore Siderurgico” by M. G. Maruccia and M . Pinzone is very interesting because it provides a General Methodology and then applies it to a specific industrial sector. This methodology, on the basis of ‘Sustainability Reporting Guidelines of GRI - The Global Reporting Initiative, proposes a general methodological approach for the identification of a set of significant process, energy, environmental and social indicators useful to characterise an industrial process, and then applies the methodological approach to the specific industrial sector of iron and steel plants, thus providing a reference for the application of a methodology to a specific industrial sector in an effective way [70].

3.2.9 FP7 and H2020 Projects

There are some EU FP funded research projects focusing on SDIs or developing sustainable development related indicators. A short summary of the notable projects including, FISSAC,

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Circular Impacts, R2PI, SCREEN, PlastiCircle, FiberEUUse and ECOBULK under H2020; and ResCoM, DESIRE, POINT, OPEN-EU and INSTREAM, under FP7 and INDI-LINK and ECODRIVE under FP6 can be found in the following discussion.

Table 13 List of EU projects related to SDIs and circular economy

List of EU projects related to SDIs and circular economy	
<i>FISSAC - Fostering Industrial Symbiosis for a Sustainable Resource Intensive Industry across the extended Construction Value Chain</i>	
Website:	http://fissacproject.eu
Programme:	Horizon 2020
Duration:	Sep 2015-Feb 2020
Summary:	FISSAC aims to develop a methodology to facilitate information exchange that supports industrial symbiosis networks in construction value chain and replicate pilot schemes at local and regional levels. An integrated industrial symbiosis management software tool will be developed to support decision making via indicator based analysis utilising life cycle approach and geo-referencing capabilities.
<i>ResCoM - Resource Conservative Manufacturing</i>	
Website:	http://www.rescoms.eu
Programme:	FP7
Duration:	Nov 2012-Oct 2017
Summary:	ResCoM, which stands for Resource Conservative Manufacturing, is working to develop an innovative methodology and software platform for the industrial implementation of closed-loop manufacturing systems. ResCoM will enable designers and manufacturers understand how collection, remanufacturing and reuse of products can lead to more profitable, resource-efficient and resilient business practices compared to the current linear manufacturing system. The platform and methodology will be complemented by a series of industrial case studies that demonstrate the benefits of its application across various industries.
<i>DESIRE - Development of a System of Indicators for a Resource Efficient Europe</i>	
Website:	fp7desire.eu
Programme:	FP7
Duration:	Sep 2012-Feb 2016
Summary:	DESIRE (Development of a System of Indicators for a Resource Efficient Europe) targeted to develop and apply an optimal set of indicators to monitor European progress towards resource-efficiency. It proposes a combination of time series of environmentally extended input output data (EE IO) and the DPSIR framework to construct the indicator set. Only this approach uses a single data set that allows for consistent construction of resource efficiency indicators capturing the EU, country, sector and product group level, and the production and consumption perspective including impacts outside the EU.
<i>INDI-LINK- Indicator-based evaluation of inter-linkages between different sustainable development objectives</i>	

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Website:	http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/84091_en.html
Programme:	FP6
Duration:	Nov 2006 – Oct 2009
Summary:	The objective of INDI-LINK Project is to improve the EU SDIs. Existing indicators under Social Inclusion; Sustainable Consumption and Production (SCP); Public Health; Sustainable Transport; and Good Governance were reviewed. Moreover, evaluation methods to assess the linkages between different priorities of the EU SDS were covered. As a result, some appraisal and evaluation methods including Strategic Environmental Assessment and cost-benefit analysis were identified suitable.
<i>POINT - Policy Influence of indicators</i>	
Website:	http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/89898_en.html
Programme:	FP7
Duration:	Apr 2008 – Jun 2011
Summary:	The objective of POINT Project is to find improved ways of using indicators in all aspects of policy, by enhancing the understanding of the factors that condition the successful use and influence of indicators in policymaking. The project focuses on the conceptual validity and reliability of indicators.
<i>IN-STREAM - INtegrating MainSTREAM Economic Indicators with those of Sustainable Development</i>	
Website:	http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/88213_en.html
Programme:	FP7
Duration:	Oct 2008 – Sep 2011
Summary:	The IN-STREAM Project aims to work on the synergies and trade-offs in economic growth and environmental sustainability via performing quantitative and qualitative assessments to establish connections between mainstream economic indicators with key well-being and sustainability indicators.
<i>OPEN-EU - One Planet Economy Network: Europe</i>	
Website:	www.oneplaneteconomynetwork.org
Programme:	FP7
Duration:	Sep 2009 – Nov 2011
Summary:	OPEN-EU Project targets to develop a “footprint family” of sustainability indicators to be placed in a scenario modelling tool for evidence-based policy. Ultimate aim is to contribute to the shift to One Planet Economy by 2050.
<i>ECODRIVE - Measuring ECO-innovation: ecological and economic performance and derived indicators</i>	
Website:	http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/84606_en.html
Programme:	FP6
Duration:	Jan 2007 – Mar 2008
Summary:	ECODRIVE Project aims to analyse the best measurement methods for eco-innovation through indicators, which should give indication of progress in terms of economic status, cost reduction, enhanced functionality, and environmental

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	performance (through reduced emissions and resource depletion among other environmental improvements).
CIRCULAR IMPACTS - Measuring the IMPACTS of the transition to the CIRCULAR economy	
Website:	circular-impacts.eu
Programme:	Horizon 2020
Duration:	Oct 2016 – Sep 2018
Summary:	CIRCULAR IMPACTS Project aims to provide European policy makers with the knowledge to guide and foster the transition to a more circular economy by developing an overarching impact assessment of that transition. The project will start by defining the circular economy, identifying the most important application areas, understanding policy needs and developing a methodology for assessing the macroeconomic and societal impacts.
R2PI - TRANSITION FROM LINEAR 2 CIRCULAR: POLICY AND INNOVATION	
Website:	www.r2piproject.eu
Programme:	Horizon 2020
Duration:	Nov 2016 – Oct 2018
Summary:	R2PI project examines the shift from the broad concept of a Circular Economy (CE) to one of a Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM) by tackling both market failure (business, consumers) and policy failure (conflicts, assumptions, unintended consequence). The goal of R2PI project is to develop sustainable business models that would facilitate the circular economy and to propose “Policy Package” that will support these business models.
SCREEN - Synergic Circular Economy across European Regions	
Website:	www.screen-lab.eu
Programme:	Horizon 2020
Duration:	Nov 2016 – Oct 2018
Summary:	SCREEN aims at the definition of a replicable systemic approach towards a transition to Circular Economy in EU regions through the identification and implementation of operational synergies between R&I investments from H2020 and the European Structural and Investment Funds, thus contributing to novel future eco-innovative and horizontal business models across different value chains.
PlastiCircle - Improvement of the plastic packaging waste chain from a circular economy approach	
Website:	http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210517_en.html
Programme:	Horizon 2020
Duration:	Jun 2017 - May 2021
Summary:	PlastiCircle project aims to develop and implement a holistic process to increase recycling rates of packaging waste in Europe. This will allow to reprocess again plastic waste in the same value chain. This process is based in four axes: collection (to increase quantity of packaging collected), transport (to reduce costs of recovered plastic), sorting (to increase quality of recovered plastic) and

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	valorisation in value-added products (i.e. foam boards, automotive parts, bituminous roofing membranes, garbage bags, asphalt sheets and urban furniture).
FiberEUse - Large scale demonstration of new circular economy value-chains based on the reuse of end-of-life fiber reinforced composites.	
Website:	http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210178_en.html
Programme:	Horizon 2020
Duration:	Jun 2017 - May 2021
Summary:	The objective of FiberEUse project is to integrate in a holistic approach different innovation actions aimed at enhancing the profitability of composite recycling and reuse in value-added products. The innovation actions are based on mechanical recycling of short glass reinforced polymer (case 1), thermal recycling of long glass and carbon fibers (case 2) and inspection repair and remanufacturing for end-of-life carbon fiber reinforced polymers in high-tech applications (case 3). The project will develop new ICT solutions for value-chain integration, scouting of new markets, analysis of legislation barriers and life cycle assessment for reverse logistic options.
ECOBULK - Circular Process for Eco-Designed Bulky Products and Internal Car Parts	
Website:	http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210181_en.html
Programme:	Horizon 2020
Duration:	Jun 2017 - May 2021
Summary:	ECOBULK project will contribute to "closing the loop" of composite products in automotive, furniture and building sectors through a large scale demonstration. The project will promote greater re-use, upgrade, refurbishment and recycle of products and materials by offering business opportunities along the entire new defined supply and value chains. The approach of the project will be based on identifying and promoting commonalities in processes, technologies, products and services ensuring replicability and transferability to other industrial sectors.

3.3 Environmental Indicators

3.3.1 Resource Efficiency Indicators

Resource efficiency is key to converging to a number of SDGs including

- Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all (Goal 7)
- Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all (Goal 8)
- Ensuring sustainable consumption and production patterns (Goal 12).

In industry, *resource efficiency* is often defined in supply chain terms, highlighting a firm's material, natural resource and energy efficiencies, and the generation and impact of waste. In some cases, only the resource efficiency of non-energy carrying materials is considered. In this

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

case, the term '*material productivity*' is used [43]. Resource efficiency in this deliverable is mainly presented under two broad resource classes; raw materials and energy.

Raw Material Consumption

Materials consumed is an important parameter to monitor the contribution to the conservation of the global resource base and efforts to reduce the material intensity and increase the efficiency of the economy. These are expressed goals of the OECD Council and various national sustainability strategies. For internal managers and others interested in the financial state of the organization, material consumption relates directly to overall costs of operation. Tracking this consumption internally, either by-product or product category, facilitates the monitoring of material efficiency and cost of material flows [70].

To address growing concern for raw material efficiency, the European Commission launched the European Raw Materials Initiative in 2008 and adopted, in 2011, a strategy document, which sets out targeted measures to secure and improve access to raw materials for the EU, based on a three-pillar approach:

- fair and sustainable supply of raw materials from international markets,
- fostering sustainable supply within the EU,
- boosting resource efficiency and promoting recycling [71].

Raw material consumption	Raw material intensity	Raw material efficiency
Absolute quantity of raw materials consumed within the system boundary for ➔ Total raw materials ➔ Primary raw materials (Renewable & non-renewable feedstock) ➔ Secondary raw materials	Specific raw material consumption per total consumption, turn over or added value ➔ Total raw materials ➔ Primary raw materials (Renewable & non-renewable feedstock) ➔ Secondary raw materials	% change in raw material intensity (i.e. specific raw material consumption) ➔ Total raw materials ➔ Primary raw materials (Renewable & non-renewable feedstock) ➔ Secondary raw materials

Figure 13 Generic classes for raw material indicators

Energy and Exergy Consumption

Energy is a fundamental aspect in resource efficiency. Key energy-related issues include dependency in fossil fuels, greenhouse gas emissions, energy security and dependency as well as cost. Promoting energy efficiency not only cuts fuel dependency but also can reduce costs and greenhouse gas emissions. Energy indicators play a crucial part in monitoring the mid-term and long-term shift towards a low-carbon economy in the EU. For this reason, energy indicators are a part of every sustainability indicator set currently in use globally.

The indicators given in Figure 14 cover energy consumption in terms of fuel, thermal energy, electricity, and renewable energy consumption. Although total fuel consumption indicators are provided below, fuel consumption indicators can be adjusted to cover fossil fuels or can be

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

further disaggregated in terms of specific types of energy sources. The set of fuel consumption indicators can be duplicated to reflect consumption of different fossil fuels if utilization trend will be monitored separately.

Energy consumption	Energy intensity	Energy efficiency
Absolute quantity of energy consumed within the system boundary for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Total energy (equivalents) ➔ Fossil fuels (non-renewable sources) ➔ Renewable energy sources ➔ Electricity 	Specific energy consumption per total consumption, turn over or added value <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Total energy (equivalents) ➔ Fossil fuels (non-renewable sources) ➔ Renewable energy sources ➔ Electricity 	% change in energy intensity (i.e. specific energy consumption) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Total energy (equivalents) ➔ Fossil fuels (non-renewable sources) ➔ Renewable energy sources ➔ Electricity

Figure 14 Generic classes for energy consumption indicators

Exergy is a measure of quality of energy and it can be consumed or destroyed through the operation of any physical or mechanical system. In thermodynamics, the term exergy is used to quantify the amount of work a unit of energy may perform relative to a thermodynamic groundstate (i.e. exergy is useful energy or energy that may theoretically be used to perform work). Here a groundstate is a state of zero theoretical work potential reached when a material or energy stream is in equilibrium with the surrounding environment.

The entropy of a resource allows us to measure the extent to which irreversible dissipation reduces the work potential (i.e. the exergy) of that resource relative to a specified groundstate. As entropy increases at constant enthalpy, exergy decreases [72]. While the groundstates of numerous substances have been estimated, the specification of thermodynamic groundstates for most resources remains highly subjective.

In order to provide a fresh take on energy indicators, exergy-based measures to monitor consumption and recycling are put forward that rely only on the calculation of exergy differentials (i.e. changes due to consumption). Exergy analysis clearly indicates the locations of energy degradation in a process and can therefore lead to improved operation or technology. Exergy analysis can also quantify the quality of heat in a waste stream. A main aim of exergy analysis is to identify meaningful (exergy) efficiencies and the causes and true magnitudes of exergy losses [73].

One way to reduce the resource depletion is to reduce the losses that accompany the transfer of exergy to consumed resources by increasing the efficiency of exergy transfer between resources, i.e., increasing the fraction of exergy removed from one resource that is transferred to another. Exergy efficiency may be thought of as a more accurate measure of energy efficiency that accounts for quantity and quality aspects of energy flows [74].

A general comparison of energy and exergy is given in Table 14.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Table 14 Comparison of energy and exergy [73]

Comparison of energy and exergy	
Energy	Exergy
Dependent of properties of only a matter or energy flow, and independent of environment properties	Dependent on properties of both matter and energy flow and the environment
Has values different from zero when in equilibrium with the environment	Equal to zero when in the dead state by virtue of being in complete equilibrium with environment
Conserved for all processes	Conserved for reversible processes and not conserved for real processes (where it is partly or completely destroyed due to irreversibilities)
Can be neither destroyed nor produced	Can be neither destroyed nor produced in a reversible process but is always destroyed (consumed) in an irreversible process
Appears in many forms (i.e. kinetic and potential energy, work , heat) and is measured in that form	Appears in many forms (i.e. kinetic and potential exergy, work , thermal exergy) and is measured in on the basis of work or ability to produce work
A measure of quantity only	A measure of both quantity and quality

Similar to energy consumption, it is possible to utilize indicators for absolute exergy consumption, exergy intensity and efficiency.

Water Consumption

Water consumption can be defined as the sum of all water drawn into the system boundaries from all sources (including surface water, ground water, rainwater, and municipal water supply) for any use [70]. While utilization of water from different sources can be monitored, reporting the total volume of water withdrawn by source contributes to an understanding of the overall scale of potential impacts and risks associated with water use. While industrial and urban activities impact water quality and quantities available, scarcity of water can also have an effect on water management systems [70].

The rate of water reuse and recycling can be a measure of efficiency and can demonstrate the success of the organization in reducing total water withdrawals and discharges. Increased reuse and recycling can result in a reduction of water consumption, treatment, and disposal costs. The reduction of water consumption through reuse and recycling can also contribute to local, national, or regional goals for managing water supplies [70].

Water consumption indicators are listed in Figure 15. Similar to secondary raw material (SRM) consumption, recycled water can be used as process water or for other purposes (grey water) and recycled water consumption should be considered when overall water utilization is being studied. Any other water sources such as rain water should be included in the assessment whenever applicable.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Water consumption	Water intensity	Water efficiency
Absolute quantity of water consumed within the system boundary for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Total water ➔ Surface water ➔ Groundwater ➔ Rain water or alternative sources ➔ Reclaimed water 	Specific water consumption per total consumption, turn over or added value <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Total water ➔ Surface water ➔ Groundwater ➔ Rain water or alternative sources ➔ Reclaimed water 	% change in water intensity (i.e. specific water consumption) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Total water ➔ Surface water ➔ Groundwater ➔ Rain water or alternative sources ➔ Reclaimed water

Figure 15 Generic classes for water consumption indicators

3.3.2 Waste and Emission Indicators

Issues related to waste generation and pollution emitted to various environmental media closely related to following SGDs.

- End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture (Goal 2)
- Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages (Goal 3)
- Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all (Goal 6)
- Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns (Goal 12).

Indicators on pollution and waste are also a part of UNEP SCP, EBI, Eurostat SDIs and EEA indicator sets.

Emissions to Air and Water

Various air pollutants released to the environment are associated with global issues including ozone depletion, acidification, eutrophication and most importantly climate change. To limit the impacts of these issues, more concrete steps were taken for ozone depletion, acidification and eutrophication, which does not necessary mean these problems are eradicated. There is still a need for monitoring of certain air emissions such as sulphur and nitrogen oxides. However, most pressing issue related to air emissions is global climate change and accordingly GHG emission indicators are included in many existing European indicator sets. Air emission indicators seen in Figure 16 covers GHG emissions apart from general category of air emissions.

GHG emissions are considered separately from air pollution indicators for two reasons. First, tackling global climate change issue is one of the core targets of not only CIRC-PACK but also many circular economy projects regardless of their TRL. Secondly, there are different approaches to monitor GHG emissions including simple inventorying, global warming potential indicators under LCIA methods and carbon footprint, which will be investigated further in the upcoming task for methodological decisions.

While quantifying GHG indicators, all GHGs should be considered and all GHG species should be converted to carbon equivalents (CO_{2-eq}). Air emissions on the other hand should be disaggregated based on the type of activities. Selection of indicators for specific air pollutants can be based on sectorial KPIs.

Assessment of wastewater generation should cover both the amount of wastewater treated to the receiving bodies after treatment as well the amount of wastewater recycled for different

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

purposes such as process water, grey water, irrigation water etc. The list of wastewater indicators in Figure 16 is strongly related to water indicators. In addition to wastewater generation, a pollutant load indicator is added to the list, which provides an indication about the wastewater quality.

Greenhouse gas emissions	Air emissions	Wastewater
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ GHG emissions in terms of CO₂-eq (total, from electricity consumed or purchased) ➔ GHG emission intensity (specific GHG emissions) ➔ Life cycle GHG indicators (to be detailed in following sections) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Air emissions reported separately for each type of pollutant within the scope ➔ Intensity of air emissions (specific air emissions, reported separately) ➔ Life cycle indicators (to be detailed in following sections) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Total wastewater generation ➔ Wastewater generation intensity (Specific wastewater generation) ➔ Wastewater recycling rate (as grey water, irrigation water etc.) ➔ Pollution load in wastewater (reported separately for each pollutant specie) ➔ Life cycle indicators (to be detailed in following sections)

Figure 16 Possible indicators for emissions to air and water

Waste and Recycling Indicators

Solid waste generation is another basic indicator that is included in many existing indicator sets. Due the difference in impact on the environment, the list proposed in Figure 17 is grouped as hazardous and non-hazardous solid wastes.

By-product indicators are in close relation to material consumption indicators, especially ones related to use of SRMs. While SRMs are valorised on the receiving end of a symbiotic material flow, by-product indicators targeting the supply end (i.e. waste/by-product generator). The reason for including a second set of indicators for a similar purpose is the possibility of losing some portion of by-products as residues if processing is required before by-products can be valorised as SRM. In this case, by-product generation on the supply end should be monitored independently.

Non-hazardous wastes	Hazardous wastes	By-products and recyclables
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Total waste generation (can be reported based on European List of Waste codes) ➔ Waste intensity (specific waste generation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Total waste generation (can be reported based on European List of Waste codes) ➔ Waste intensity (specific waste generation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Rate of recycling and rate of landfilling (can be reported separately for hazardous and non-hazardous wastes or waste codes) ➔ Efficiency of valorization as a result of recycling processes

Figure 17 Possible waste indicators (The term “rate” in above indicators refers to the % of total waste flow according to [44])

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

3.3.3 LCA Indicators

The life cycle indicators, LCA indicators in particular, presented in this Section are used to carry out quantitative assessments for different aspects of environmental issues similar to the indicators listed in the previous sub-section. The main difference between the life cycle indicators and the proposed indicators in tables above is mainly the system boundaries for which the assessment is done. The environmental and economic indicators already discussed follow a gate-to-gate approach, where data required for quantification can be simply obtained via material and energy flow analyses within the confines of the company. However, life cycle indicators, quantified either for the product or the production process, use a wider and holistic scope covering the life cycle of the product or process.

In an LCA study, the flows to and from a functional system are assigned to various impact categories based on their possible environmental effects. Material input and outputs of the selected system can have multiple environmental impacts. For instance, chlorofluorocarbons can cause both global climate change and stratospheric ozone depletion or NO_x and ammonia compounds can lead to acidification and eutrophication at the same time [75]. Therefore, the list of impact categories or ecological indicators in an LCA study should be selected based on the life cycle inventory and their relevance to the possible effects created by the materials consumed or emitted.

According ISO 14040-4 Standards [76][77]:

- The selection of impact categories, category indicators and characterization models shall be both justified and consistent with the goal and scope of the LCA;
- The selection of impact categories shall reflect a comprehensive set of environmental issues related to the product system being studied.

Here it is important to differentiate two classes of impact categories; midpoint and endpoint indicators. Midpoint impact assessment models reflect the relative potency of the stressors at a common midpoint within the cause-effect chain. Analysis at midpoint minimizes the amount of forecasting and effect modelling incorporated into the LCIA [78], however, the high number of possible midpoint indicators requires the LCA practitioner to identify relevant impact categories. On the other hand, although endpoint indicators (human health, ecosystem and resources) are simpler and easier to communicate, there are many underlying assumptions and high level of uncertainty during aggregation of midpoint set to endpoint indicators. Furthermore, due to aggregation, all midpoint indicators, whether relevant or not, have to be included in the study. Midpoint modelling can minimize assumptions and value choices, reflect a higher level of societal consensus, and be more comprehensive than model coverage for endpoint estimation [79]. Therefore, two methodological choices need to be made during scope definition; first one being whether midpoint or endpoint assessment will be conducted and if midpoint assessment will be used, which midpoint ecological indicators will be selected.

Figure 18 Example for environmental mechanisms in midpoint and endpoint assessment (Adapted from [75])

Figure 19 Level of aggregation in midpoint and endpoint assessment (Adapted from [80])

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Life Cycle Indicators and Life Cycle Impact Assessment Methods

One of the key steps of LCA is to select the appropriate impact indicators relevant for the goal and scope of the specific LCA study. Although the selection of impact indicators is carried out during initial goal and scope definition stage according to ISO 14040-44 standards, due to iterative nature of the LCA methodology, the list of impact indicators are often finalized in the following stages of LCA based on the system boundaries, preliminary LCA results and data availability/quality issues.

After impact indicators are selected, next step is to decide on the impact assessment methods to be utilized for quantification of indicators. A wide variety of impact assessment methods are available with different approaches to estimate the environmental mechanisms and impact factors.

Table 15 presents the number of indicators within some widely utilized impact assessment methodologies.

Table 15 Impact assessment methods and numbers of indicators [95]

Impact assessment methods and numbers of indicators		
Category	Impact assessment methods	Number of indicators
Midpoint indicators	CML 2001	49
	EDIP 2003	21
	IMPACT 2002	14
	ReCiPe	31
	TRACI	9
Endpoint indicators	Ecoinicator 99	3
	Ecological scarcity 2013	1
	EPS 2000	1
	IMPACT 2002	3
	ReCiPe	3
Resource footprints	Fossil energy footprint	1
	Water footprint	1
	Material footprint	1
	Land footprint	1

The best practice is to select the most suitable impact assessment method for each indicator. For this purpose, EU Joint Research Centre has conducted a study on recommendations for life cycle impact assessment in the European context for which the draft report was published in

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

2011 with no subsequent editions to be best of the knowledge of authors of this report [96]. Although it is dated, this report provides a good insight on the recommended impact methods for different impact categories.

Literature is reviewed for LCA studies performed for plastic packaging material. System boundaries and life cycle indicators / impact assessment methods selected for each study are summarised in Table 16.

Table 16 LCA indicators used in previous studies

LCA indicators used in previous studies			
Scope	System boundaries	Life Cycle Indicators / Impact Assessment Methods	Reference
Food waste packaging	Cradle-to-grave	GHG emissions Energy consumption Waste generation	[81]
Beverage packaging system	Cradle-to-grave	GHG emissions Human toxicity potential Ozone creation potential	[82]
Biodegradable packaging material	Cradle-to-recycling	Endpoint assessment (Human health, ecosystem quality, resources)	[83]
Recycling of bio-based plastic packaging materials	Streamlined (Production + disposal)	GHG emissions	[84]
Composite packaging materials	Cradle-to-grave	Endpoint assessment (Human health, ecosystem quality, resources)	[85]
Composite packaging materials	Cradle-to-grave (streamlined)	IMPACT 2002+ midpoint indicators and bulk waste from EDIP 2003 method. Both midpoint and endpoint assessment was conducted	[86]
Recycling packaging food waste	Cradle-to-farm	GHG emissions Energy consumption Waste generation	[87]
EoL of two biodegradable packaging material	EoL Cradle-to-gate	IMPACT 2002+ LCIA indicators GHG emissions Energy consumption	[88]
Two Packaging material	Cradle-to-grave	ReCiPe LCIA indicators	[89]
Recycling packaging waste	Cradle-to-grave	ReCiPe CML 2001 IPCC GWP 100A USEtox CED	[90]

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

The most related LCA indicators are summarized below keeping in mind that due to iterative nature of the LCA methodology, the list of impact indicators are often finalized in the following stages of LCA based on the system boundaries, preliminary LCA results and data availability/quality issues.

Carbon footprint / Global warming potential

GHG emissions and resulting global climate change issue is monitored through indicators including carbon footprint, global climate change potential and global warming potential. All of these indicators report total GHG emissions in terms of carbon dioxide equivalents. The methodologies of estimation are outlined in ISO 14040, 14044 and 14067 Standards. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change is periodically releasing the characterisation factors for conversion of GHG emissions to carbon dioxide equivalents.

Cumulative energy demand (CED)

The CED represents the direct and indirect energy use, including the energy consumed during the extraction, manufacturing and disposal of the raw and auxiliary materials. It is often measured from cradle to (factory) gate, cradle to site (of use), or cradle to grave (end of life). The total CED is composed of the fossil cumulative energy demand (i.e., from hard coal, lignite, peat, natural gas, and crude oil) and the CED of nuclear, biomass, water, wind, and solar energy in the life cycle [91]. Unit of quantification for CED is MJ/functional unit (FU). CED provides a basis for comparison between different products with the same function and is commonly utilized for reporting environmental performance of construction materials.

Environmentally weighted material consumption (EMC)

The development of the Environmentally weighted Material Consumption (EMC) was commissioned by the European Commission (EC) in order to evaluate the option to develop an economy-wide indicator, which could describe in a quantitative manner the decoupling of environmental impacts of global resource use from economic growth by the EU.

EMC provides an aggregate measure of the life-cycle-wide environmental impacts associated with the domestic material consumption of (a set of) selected materials. For the life cycle inventories, data sets from the Ecoinvent database were used in the project. 13 available impact categories (GWP, ODP etc.) per unit of material and energy carrier use are normalized with data on status quo of a reference year on the global level; these normalized impact coefficients are multiplied with the apparent consumption of a set of selected materials and energy carriers. To arrive at one score, the 13 environmental impact categories have to be aggregated using weighting. [92]

Abiotic Resource Depletion (fossil)

Abiotic resource depletion covers the use of both non-renewable and renewable abiotic resources. Considering the fossil resources depletion, the decrease in the natural fossil resources and the protection of the natural resources are the key issues. The characterisation model is a

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

function of natural reserves and the rate of extraction basically. The energy content of the fossil fuels is the main input when assessing the Abiotic Resource Depletion of fossil resources. The characterisation factor for the assessment is defined as the Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP) which is derived for each extraction of fossil fuels in equivalent of depletion of “antimony” element as reference. Therefore, LCI results, extraction of fossil fuels (in kg) are multiplied by the characterisation factor (in kg antimony equivalents/kg extraction) to obtain the indicator result.[93]

Human Toxicology

In life cycle impact assessment, the effects related to the human toxicity impact category are focused on effects resulting from direct exposure to chemicals regarding the fate, exposure, potency (i.e. dose-response) and severity of the material. In order to evaluate the resulting effects on human health, assessing the human toxicology in terms of relative impacts of emissions associated with product life cycle is best described by using comparable indicators.

Toxicological characterisation factors for human health are calculated by taking into account the time-integrated fate, exposure of a unit mass of chemical released into the environment (including, in many cases, the size of the exposed population), toxicological potency (a quantitative measure related to the dose–response of a chemical, such as the LOEL – the Lowest Observable Effect Level in a test) and toxicological severity (a measure or description, qualitative or quantitative, of the effect incurred, such as bladder cancer or skin irritation). The toxicological indicator of each substance emitted must be additive in order to aggregate the indicator results of the many different emissions occurring throughout a life cycle. [94]

3.4 Economic Indicators

The list of economic indicators is provided in Table 17. Among these indicators, production volume, turnover and net value added are commonly used for normalization purposes as denominator, i.e. obtaining specific or intensity indicators from total consumption/generation indicators.

Table 17 Generic economic indicators

Economic indicators	
Production volume /capacity	In tonnes or m3 per year
Turnover	Turnover (revenue) represents the sales made by a company of its products/services in a period, which can be a month, quarter, half-year or full year. Turnover is usually expressed in monetary terms. The term is often just referred to as sales or net sales, which means revenues without VAT. It is different from “profit” which is the residual earnings of a business after all expenses have been charged against net sales. In monetary units.
Net added value	Net value added has different meanings in different fields like economics,

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	<p>statistics or development studies. In business economics, net value added is obtained by deducting consumption of fixed capital (or depreciation charges) from gross value added which is the (revenue – cost of goods and services purchased) [97]. The resulting figure is defined in monetary units as follows:</p> <p>Net value added = Revenue – Cost of goods and services purchased – Depreciation on tangible assets</p>
CAPEX (Capital cost)	<p>Possible indicators under CAPEX</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total capital cost (in monetary units) • Specific capital cost (in monetary units)
OPEX (Operational cost)	<p>Possible indicators under OPEX (can be total or specific in monetary units)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material cost (can be reported separately for primary and secondary raw materials) • Water cost • Energy cost • Land use cost • Labour cost • Maintenance and replacement cost • Total OPEX • Disposal costs (or cost savings after interventions) • Water treatment costs (or cost savings after interventions) • GHG emission costs (can be taxes, penalties or cost savings after interventions) • Other environmental costs including regulatory fines • Revenues resulting from new products/services
Net present value (NPV)	Considers both CAPEX and OPEX
Return on investment (ROI)	
Internal rate of return on investments (IRR)	
LCC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life cycle cost itself is the only indicator obtained under life cycle costing methodology. As explained earlier, it is based on NPV calculation and it combines a number of basic economic indicators including OPEX and CAPEX. • The LCC value can be normalized by using production value or net added value combining further basic economic indicators within the LCC framework. • The main difference between simple NPV calculation and LCC is the scope of the assessment. The environmental externalities and whole life cycle of the product or service in question are often missed in

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	<p>basic NPV calculations focusing mostly on the investment and operational expenses born upon the investor.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> On the contrary, LCC (or WLC depending on the LCC approach chosen by the practitioner) aims to identify environmental and social cost of the functional system analysed whenever possible in addition to apparent cost of investment. Under LCC, costs inflicted upon different stakeholders (such as investors, public in general and specific stakeholder groups that are impacted from the effects of the project or product life cycle etc.) can be identified separately through careful consideration of apparent and hidden cost items.
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3.5 Social Indicators

In this section, Social Indicators are covered under Social Life Cycle (S-LCA) Indicators as main frame. According to the data gathered from product's life cycle stages, a set of inventory social indicators are used and each one of them specifically denotes the desired qualitative and quantitative output [97]. Considering the Social Impact Indicators, five type of stakeholder groups identify sub-categories; Worker, Local Community, Society, Value Chain Actors and Consumer. There are also relevant impact categories Human Rights, Working Conditions, Health and Safety, Cultural Heritage, Governance and Socioeconomic Repercussions. For most of the subcategory social indicators location information is a requirement as they are sensitive to the location. The location information may not need to be exact, may only illustrate the country or region where production occurs. Thus, indicators should be classified as "site specific" or "generic", where "generic" includes global social "hotspots" (e.g. child labour) [26]

The table below illustrates the social indicators being assessed in accordance with the relevant stakeholder group.

Table 18 Social Indicators with respect to relevant Stakeholder Groups (Adapted from [23])

Social Indicators with respect to relevant Stakeholder Groups		
Stakeholder Group	UNEP / SETAC Subcategory	Site Specific Only
Worker	Freedom of association and collective bargaining	
	Child labour	
	Fair Salary	
	Working hours	
	Forced labour	
	Equal opportunities/Discrimination	
	Health & Safety	

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	Social benefits/Social Security	
	Education and Training	
	Management system	Yes
Consumer	Health & Safety	
	Feedback mechanism	Yes
	Consumer privacy	
	Transparency	Yes
	End of Life responsibility	
Local Community	Access to material resources	
	Access to immaterial resources	
	Delocalization and Migration	
	Cultural heritage	
	Safe and healthy living conditions	
	Respect of Indigenous rights	
	Community engagement	Yes
	Local employment	Yes
	Secure living conditions	
Society	Public commitments to sustainability issues	Yes
	Contribution to economic development	
	Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts	
	Technology development	
	Corruption	
Value Chain Actors	Fair Competition	Yes
	Promoting social responsibility	
	Supplier relationships	Yes
	Respect of intellectual property rights	

Furthermore, "The Social Hotspots Database" [98] contains country and sector-specific indicator tables to help identify hotspots, the countries and sectors of concern, in supply chains based on potential social impacts. Twenty Social Theme Tables have been established for the database. The "Social Themes" were chosen with respect to recommendations in The Guidelines, which were informed by the International Policy Frameworks (International Conventions, Covenants and Declarations). The Tables include indicator data and characterised risk for social impacts

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

such as forced labour, prohibition of freedom of association, excessive working time, and lack of community services etc.

Table 19 Social Indicators in accordance with the related Subcategory [98]

Social Indicators in accordance with the related Subcategory			
Category	Subcategory (Social Theme)	Data Indicator	Characterised Issue
Labour Rights and Decent Work	Labour Laws/Conventions	Number of Labour Laws	Risk of country not passing Labour laws by sector
		Number of Labour Laws by Sector	Risk of country not passing Labour laws by sector
		Number of Labour Conventions Ratified	Risk of country not adopting Labour Conventions by Sector
		Number of Labour Conventions Ratified by sector	Risk of country not adopting Labour Conventions by Sector
		Year of last minimum Wage Update	Risk of minimum Wage not being updated
	Wage Assessment	Minimum Wages (USD)	Risk of Country Average Wage being < Minimum Wage
		Average Unskilled Wages (USD) in country	
		Non-poverty Guideline (USD)	Risk of Country Average Wage being < Non-poverty Guideline
		Average Unskilled Wages (USD) in country	
		Minimum Wages (USD)	Risk of Sector Average Wage being < Minimum Wage
		Average Unskilled Wages (USD) by sector	
		Non-poverty Guideline (USD)	Risk of Sector Average Wage being < Non-poverty Guideline
		Average Unskilled Wages (USD) by sector	
	Population living in poverty	Percent of Population living on <\$2/day	Risk of Population living on <\$2/day
	Child Labour	Child labour % in country	Risk of child labour in country
Child labour % by sector		Risk of child labour by sector	

Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	Forced Labour	Qualitative	Risk of forced labour in country
		Qualitative	Risk of forced labour by sector
	Excessive Working Time	Percent Working>48 hours/week in country	Risk of population working>48 hours/week in country
		Qualitative	Risk of population working>48 hours/week by sector
	Freedom of Association, Collective Bargaining, Right to Strike	Qualitative	Risk of not having Freedom of Association rights
		Qualitative	Risk of not having Collective Bargaining rights
		Qualitative	Risk of not having the Right to Strike
	Unemployment	Unemployment average % in country (in a time period)	Risk of high unemployment in country
		Unemployment % by sector	Risk of high unemployment by sector
	Governance	Legal System	World Bank Worldwide Governance Indicator - Rule of Law
Bertelsmann Transformational Index - Rule of Law, Independent Judiciary			
CIRI Human Rights Index - Independent Judiciary			
Global Integrity Index - Judicial Accountability			
Global Integrity Index - Rule of Law			
Global Integrity Index - Law Enforcement			
World Justice Project - Average			
Human Rights	Indigenous Rights	Presence of Indigenous Population, X	Not characterised

Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

		Indigenous Population %	Amount of Indigenous Population
		ILO Convention adopted for Indigenous, Y or N	Risk of country not adopting Indigenous ILO convention and UN Declaration
		UN Declaration for Indigenous, endorsed (Y), abstained (A), against (N)	
		Number of laws enacted to protect Indigenous	Risk of country not passing Laws to protect Indigenous
		Qualitative	Risk of Indigenous Rights Infringements by sector
	Gender Equity	Social Institutions and Gender Index	Risk of Gender Inequity
		Global Gender Gap	
		World Bank Gender Development Indicator	
		World Bank Gender Empowerment Index	
		CIRI Human Rights Index - Economic	
		CIRI Human Rights Index - Political	
		CIRI Human Rights Index - Social	
		Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1000 women between ages 15-19)	Not characterised
		Fertility rate, total (births per women)	Not characterised
Share of women employed in the non-agricultural sector (% of total non-agricultural employment)	Not characterised		
% Unemployment (% of female labour force unemployed, % of male labour force unemployed)	Not characterised		

Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

		% of women workers vs. men by sector	Risk of Gender Inequity by sector
	High Conflict Zones	Heidelberg Conflict Barometer - # of conflicts	Risk for high conflict
		Heidelberg Conflict Barometer - maximum intensity of conflicts (1-5)	
		Heidelberg Conflict Barometer - change in conflicts (positive = worsening)	
		Number of Refugees - UN Refugee Agency (000's)	
		Center for Systemic Peace Indicator	
		Minority Rights Group Indicators	
		Top Risers from last year in Minority Rights Group Indicator, X	
		Qualitative	
	Human Health - Communicable Diseases and other Health Risks besides Disease	Life expectancy at birth (years)	Risk of low life expectancy
		Mortality rates for injuries (per 100000 population/year)	Risk of high mortality rates due to injuries
		Proportion of undernourished % of total population, (-) =<5% (year)	Risk of high undernourishment
		Deaths due to indoor and outdoor air and water pollution, per million (in years)	Risk of death due to air and water pollution
		Population affected by natural disasters, ave per year per million per years	Risk of death due to natural disasters
		Cases of HIV (per 1000 adults of 15-49 years old)	Risk of HIV

Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

		per year)	
		Cases of Tuberculosis (per 100000 population per year)	Risk of Tuberculosis
		Cases of Malaria (per 100000 population per year)	Risk of Malaria
		Cases of Dengue Fever (per 100000 population per year)	Risk of Dengue Fever
		Cases of Cholera (per year)	Risk of Cholera
		Mortality rates from communicable diseases (per 100000 population per year)	Risk of mortality from communicable diseases
Community Infrastructure	Children out of School	Children out of School - male	Risk of Children not attending School - male
		Children out of School - female	Risk of Children not attending School - female
		Children out of School - total	Risk of Children not attending School - total
	Access to improved Drinking Water	Access to improved Drinking Water, %rural	Risk of not having access to improved Drinking Water - rural
		Access to improved Drinking Water, %urban	Risk of not having access to improved Drinking Water - urban
		Access to improved Drinking Water, %total	Risk of not having access to improved Drinking Water - total
	Access to improved Sanitation	Access to improved Sanitation, %rural	Risk of not having access to improved Sanitation - rural
		Access to improved Sanitation, %urban	Risk of not having access to improved Sanitation - urban
		Access to improved Sanitation, %total	Risk of not having access to improved Sanitation - total
	Access to	Access to Hospital Beds -	Risk of not having access to

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	Hospital Beds	# of beds/1000 pop	Hospital Beds
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3.6 Circularity Indicators

3.6.1 Linear Flow/Circular Flow Index

Linear flow index (LFI) provides insight on how linear a production model is, which is represented by the proportion of material flowing in a linear manner from virgin materials to unrecoverable waste. This proportion is calculated by dividing the total amount of materials flowing in a linear way by total amount of materials within the entire production system collectively comprised of linear and circular fashions (i.e. total mass flow). This index results in values between 0 and 1 where 1 is a complete linear flow and 0 is complete restorative flow. [3]

$$LFI = \frac{V + W}{2M + \frac{W_F - W_c}{2}}$$

Where LFI: linear flow index

V: Mass of virgin feedstock used in a product

W: Mass of unrecoverable waste associated with a product

M: Mass of a product

W_F : Mass of unrecoverable waste generated when producing recycled feedstock for a product

W_c : Mass of unrecoverable waste generated in the process of recycling parts of a product

3.6.2 Product Utility

Utility accounts for the length of a product's use phase (lifetime) and intensity of use (function). The length of useful lifetime can be defined as the ratio of lifetime of the product in question to average lifetime of the similar products with same function on the market. The intensity reflects the extent to which a product is used to its full capacity and can be considered as the number of times it serves its function before it reaches the end-of-life stage, which is achieved through recycling. Therefore, intensity should not be confused with repetitive undertaking of a task before the product becomes a waste. Similar to useful lifetime, intensity can be calculated by taking the ratio of number of times a product serves its function before it reaches the definitive end-of-life to the same number calculated for the average of the products on the market [3]. Utility is calculated as

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

$$X = \frac{L}{L_{av}} * \frac{U}{U_{av}}$$

Where L: lifetime of the product

L_{av} : average lifetime of the similar products on the market

U: number of times function served over the lifetime

U_{av} : average number of times function is served over the lifetime by similar products on the market

While using this indicator, it is important to make sure that any given effect is only considered once either as an impact on lifetimes, or on intensity of use. [3]

3.6.3 Material Circularity Indicator

Material circularity indicator (MCI) measures how circular a production system and how long and intensely the product in question is being used. It is comprised of the amount of virgin materials used during production stage, amount of unrecoverable waste generated at the end of product life cycle and utility factor explained in previous section. [3]

The virgin feedstock consumption is calculated from

$$V = M(1 - F_R - F_U)$$

Where V: Mass of virgin feedstock used in a product

M: Mass of a product

F_R : Fraction of mass of a product's feedstock from recycled sources

F_U : Fraction of mass of a product's feedstock from reused sources

In order to estimate the unrecoverable waste, it is necessary to consider the collection rate of product for recycling, fraction of product sent to landfilling and energy recovery, efficiency of recycling process as well as the waste generated through such processes. Consequently, overall amount of unrecoverable waste can be determined by

$$W = W_0 + \frac{W_F + W_C}{2}$$

Where W: Mass of unrecoverable waste

W_0 : Mass of unrecoverable waste through a product's material going into landfill, waste to energy and any other type of process where the materials are no longer recoverable

W_F : Mass of unrecoverable waste generated when producing recycled feedstock for a product

W_C : Mass of unrecoverable waste generated in the process of recycling parts of a product

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Moreover, in order to evaluate material circularity indicator of a product, a factor $F(X)$ depending on the utility of the product (X) should be defined;

$$F(X) = \frac{0.9}{X}$$

Where $F(X)$: Utility factor built as a function of the utility X of a product. Also note that the function F should hence have the form $\frac{a}{X}$ for some constant a . Setting $a = 0.9$ ensures that the MCI takes, by convention, the value 0.1 for a fully linear product (i.e., $LFI = 1$) whose utility equals the industry average (i.e., $X = 1$)

As a result, Material Circulatory Indicator then can be evaluated by;

$$MCI = 1 - LFI \cdot F(X)$$

3.6.4 Resource Productivity

European Commission's Roadmap to Resource Efficient Europe (2011), which aims to improve economic performance while reducing the pressure on natural resources, proposes "resource productivity" as a provisional lead indicator together with a series of impact based indicators [100].

Resource productivity is measured by the ratio of GDP to Domestic Material Consumption and is expressed in Euro/tonne. Higher the resource productivity, better the performance, with growth consuming relatively fewer resources. However, this indicator only captures the material resources aspects and does involve other resources or the potential shift of burden across countries [100].

3.6.5 Value-based Resource Efficiency

Maio et al. (2017) criticizes the material flow indicators since they do not support decision making. Economic value, which is an extensively important parameter for decision making, should be used to measure resource efficiency. Unlike mass representing only the quantity, economic value involves both quantity and quality, i.e., environmental and social value. Monetary value embodies environmental costs and other external costs by means of taxes and permits and also enables policy makers to identify and effectively monitor stressed resources. Moreover, social value is also included in economic value through the mechanism of taxes and incentives. The proposed value-based resource efficiency (VRE) indicator is formulated as value added divided by monetary value of all inputs where the monetary value is price times the physical volume. [101]

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

$$VRE = \frac{Y}{\sum_i W_i X_i} = \frac{GO - II}{\sum_i W_i X_i}$$

Where

Y: output value (at process level: value added of the industry along the value chain and at product level: final selling price times the number of units of final production).

X_i: resources in volumes

W_i: weights (can be taken as price (p_i) which indirectly reflects both environmental and social impact of the input)

GO: gross output

II: intermediate inputs (energy (E), materials (M) and services (S))

$$VRE = \frac{GO - E - M - S}{E + M} = \frac{GO - S}{E + M} - 1 = \frac{GO - S}{p_E X_E + p_M X_M} - 1$$

3.6.6 Resource Duration / Longevity

Franklin et al. (2016) comments that current indicators based on burden of a product relative to its value are not adequate to evaluate circular economy and suggests a new performance metric called longevity indicator. Longevity covers the initial lifetime in use, earned refurbishment lifetime and earned recycled lifetime. Longevity indicates time to measure the retention of a material within a product system, where greater retention means that the use of the resource is maximised. Longevity can be utilized by companies to evaluate their contribution to circular economy or for material selection in design phase to enable continued material and product retention. [102]

Critical shortcomings of longevity are: (i) it assumes all returned recycled material is used to produce the same product (i.e., ignores down-cycling), (ii) additional material input (new or recycled) in refurbishment stage is not addressed and (iii) it does not cover any monetary value such as economic return [90].

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

4 DECISION SUPPORT TOOLS

Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)

MCI was developed by Ellen MacArthur Foundation for European companies in order to analyse their products and/or business models with respect to Circular Economy concept. The tool is based on Excel calculation sheet and one can assess the circularity performance either on the product level or on the company level. [99]

The Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) for a product evaluates the degree to which linear flow has been minimised and restorative flow maximised for its component materials. MCI also shows how long and intensively it is used compared to a similar industry-average product. In particular, MCI is established from a combination of three product characteristics: the mass of virgin raw material used in manufacture, the mass of unrecoverable waste that is referred to the product, and a utility factor that denotes the length and intensity of the product's use. Thus, any product that is manufactured using only virgin feedstock and ends up in landfill at the end of its use phase can be considered a fully 'linear' product. Similarly, any product that contains no virgin feedstock, is completely collected for recycling or component reuse, and where the recycling efficiency is 100% can be considered a fully 'circular' product.

In practice, most products will sit somewhere between these two extremes. The Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) gives a single score between 0 and 1 where higher values show a higher circularity. The following inputs are used to evaluate the MCI:

- Input in the production process: How much input is coming from virgin and recycled materials and reused components?
- Utility during use phase: How long and intensively is the product used compared to an industry average product of similar type? This takes into account increased durability of products, but also repair/ maintenance and shared consumption business models.
- Destination after use: How much material goes into landfill (or energy recovery), how much is collected for recycling, which components are collected for reuse?
- Efficiency of recycling: How efficient are the recycling processes used to produce recycled input and to recycle material after use?

Along with the methodology, a commercially-available web-based tool is also developed for businesses to calculate their progress in ensuring that their products fit a circular economy based business model. Users can import, build or edit the data in the MS Office Excel sheet in accordance with their products or designs.

Circular Economy Toolkit (CET)

CET is a free, online circularity assessment tool to illustrate the potential improvements in terms of circularity of a product. The tool includes 33 questions in 7 sub categories in a trinary format, such as "yes/partly/no" or "high/medium/low". The content of the questions are related to design, manufacture and distribute (7), usage (3), maintenance and repair (6), reuse and

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

redistribution (3), refurbish and remanufacture (10), product-as-a-service (2), recycling at the end-of-life (2) [104].

The CET has merged literature, survey results and observations from workshops done for circularity evaluations. The assessment tool will end up with an indicator output of potential areas for business opportunity or improvement according to the product design and your business operations. Considering the product design, manufacture, usage and recycling phases, a ranking is placed according to an average of the results.

Moreover, CET illustrates the opportunities (including financial viability and market growth potential) from the results of the existing services (maintain/repair, reuse/redistribute, refurbish/remanufacture and products as a service) in contrast to the current product design. If there is high business opportunity and the product design is well suited, it's rated as a potential 'high opportunity'. If there is little business opportunity and the product design does not aid the service, then it is ranked as a lower opportunity.

CET has been established to capture current product design and business operations. Any change occurred in either stage will affect the size of the opportunity in the output. To illustrate, although there is a strong market for remanufactured goods, the product design does not support remanufacture, hence the opportunity will be ranked low. Similarly, if a product redesign with strong remanufacture structure, i.e. easier to disassemble and more modular in design, then the opportunity would increase.

Furthermore, CET considers the results against best practice, (e.g. using 100% fully recycled materials is excellent for the Circular Economy) which might be technologically impossible to achieve. The assessment tool is unable to assess the difficulty for a business to further stretch the product or service performance. This needs to be covered in more thorough discussions and analysis.

The tool also does not take the customer tendencies into account such that, if the product is sold to the consumer market then there may be a greater opportunity to sell more sustainable products which could be sold at a premium. In that sense, CET offers a simple grading of opportunities, which may yield more accurate solutions when combined with other reliable tools.

Circular Economy Indicator Prototype (CEIP)

Griffiths and Cayzer (2016) developed CEIP tool in order to evaluate the circularity performance of a product. The tool was designed on Excel calculation sheet and based on point-based questionnaire. In total, fifteen (weighted) question have five subgroups of the life cycle stages of the product; design or redesign, manufacturing, commercialisation, usage and end-of-life. After completing the questionnaire, the tool results in an overall circularity performance of the product and a spider diagram to show detailed performance evaluations on different life cycle stages as well [105].The CEIP was designed in MS Office Excel through the following steps:

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Step 1 – Question and Answer criteria configuration: the criteria of the questions and answers of CEIP is designed where every variable should be evaluated with one question. Moreover, the responses to the question are not open and they are pre-designed. Every question has an ideal response option which is assigned to the all available points for that question. Similarly, every question has a least preferred response option which doesn't take any available points.

Step 2 – Question Design: the questions should be highly focused in calculating the performance of the product within the CE principles/ categories. Each product lifecycle stage includes specific questions for that particular stage. The CEIP contains 15 questions in total.

Step 3 – Answer Options Design: the answer options is the key design step because those answers represent the alternatives that create the scale from being “non-circular at all” to being “the ideal circular option”. Therefore, the design of the answer options starts with the definition of the “Ideal Final Result” (IFR) of the variable that is being addressed. To illustrate, the IFR was identified using the insights from the interviews, the literature review and the benchmark of the previous models. The response options are intended to form a coherent and reasonable scale of improvements from the less circular option to the circular IFR. Due to the “openness” nature of the question several options can be designed, therefore, a selection process must be carried out to deliver the most representative ones. Furthermore, the responses should intend to be the most general possible in order to be able to evaluate products from different industries and contexts. This condition was perhaps one of the most difficult challenges while designing the responses options.

Step 4 – Weighting: Firstly, defining how much points from the available points of the test (152 points maximum) should correspond to each variable/question. The idea that was followed was basically to intend distribute an equal amount of points to each lifecycle stage of the products. On the other hand, from the lifecycle stages, it was inferred by the literature review and the interviews that some of the stages are slightly more relevant to the CE principles than others. Within this regard, lifecycle stages like “In Use” and “End of Use” got 35 points each one to distribute within their variables. It is assumed that actions within those stages would produce bigger impacts in increasing the performance of products within the CE principles. The final distribution of available points through the lifecycle stages is: Design/Redesign 27 points, Manufacturing 25 points, Commercialisation 30 points, In Use 35 points and End of Use 35 points out of 152 points in total.

Resource Conservative Manufacturing (RESCOM) (Under Development)

RESCOM is a collaborative software package project – under the consortium of 12 partners from research, industry and technology – (Grant Agreement No: 603843) aiming to provide a well-designed decision support tool in terms of circularity, product life cycle management and material information management. The project targets to enable applicable circular design tools in order to guide the companies by showing the positive impacts of closed-loop product systems in terms of economic value added, resource efficiency, CO₂ emissions and energy use. RESCOM combines both software and non-software (descriptive) tools with up-to-date features

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

as Circularity Calculator, Circularity Pathfinder, Risk Analyser, Planning and Simulation and Forecasting tools. Thus, RESCOM aims to support the companies to explore improved business models and understand the best design practices for multiple life cycles. [106]

RESCOM is developed with important tools responsible for different actions as follows;

The Analytical Tool helps manufacturers to analyse the potential profitability and environmental performance of conventional linear models in contrast with potential closed-loop scenarios. A number of parameters with respect to cost (e.g. production costs, forward and reverse logistics costs) and critical factors (e.g. remanufacturing success rate, return rate) can be used to test different scenarios. Investment costs for design, reverse engineering, or facilities can also be taken into consideration where needed. CO₂ evaluations provide insights into scenario of the product's environmental performance.

The Circular Pathfinder is the first tool for companies desiring to occupy circular economy thinking. It allows them to analyse and define the most appropriate circular pathways for their products, by answering a number of questions provided. The Circular Pathfinder helps the user towards circular pathways that have potential in their specific case with the best practices of others in the tool. It shows why certain pathways, such as product remanufacturing, life extension, or recycling are of interest, with examples from companies that have already applied them, and suggests further steps to take.

The purpose of the *Circularity Calculator* is to guide designers that work in the complex product development phase to obtain a 'circularity instinct': a knowledge of how strategic design decisions affect the degree of circularity of resource flows and potential value capture within the product-service-system.

The Circularity Calculator tool illustrates the potential mass and value flows of a product regarding whether the various parts are either reused, remanufactured and/or recycled. The tool also help designers to model different conceptual design solutions and business models to explore and compare design scenarios and see their impact on performance indices such as overall circularity, recycling rate and value recovery potential. The calculator can make not only high level but also more detailed analyses, thus it helps to generate ideas and recommendations and to provide timely results.

MI:BoM Analyzer aims to assess the environmental, regulatory, and supply chain risks, and can support increased resource efficiency for products. By importing a "bill of materials" (BoM) the tool can directly run reports that apply an extensive database of materials, process, and environmental data to assess product risk and, therefore guide design decisions. Enhanced Eco Audit reports assess environmental impacts and cost across multiple use cycles, providing detailed information on reverse logistics and estimating the break-even point for closed loop remanufacturing against linear production, regarding both environmental impacts and lifecycle cost as well.

The Multi-method Simulation Tool is designed for assessing the economic and environmental performance of circular products from an overall system perspective. The tool takes over 120

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

variables simultaneously into account using system dynamics and agent based modelling. Accordingly, the output helps designers and manufacturers to consider the effects of, and to address challenges related to customer acceptance and expected demand of new business models, effects of product design alternatives, and supply chain design to suggest a new business models.

The Reman Design Checklist is established for product engineers to consider the remanufacturability of a product design by evaluating and scoring the remanufacturability of its components: information that helps the team to track progress between design iterations. The output of the tool includes an evaluation of product components and recommendations for further improvement.

The Upgrade Forecast tool is modelled to help OEMs determine what upgrade specifications to include in product design. The tool enables interdisciplinary teams involved in product development to show future trends, demands and disturbances, to point out the product features that will require upgrading, and to resolve the specifications of these future upgrades.

Eco-Industrial Park Environmental Support System (EPESUS)

EPESUS is an ICT platform for environmental and economic sustainability assessment with real time and spatial big data analysis capabilities. EPESUS Software is capable of identifying the material and energy flows throughout the life cycle processes of products and determine the environmental impacts through LCA. It provides assistance in the fulfillment of environmental requirements and boosting the competitiveness of industrial establishments in the international domain. Sustainability assessment in EPESUS is based upon life cycle methodologies including LCA and LCC. In addition to LCA and LCC modules, EPESUS graphical user interfaces modules have been developed.

EPESUS can provide,

- Reduction of cost of manufacturing and life cycle costs of products
- Support for environmental compliance
- Adoption of new circular economy models
- Implementation of cleaner production strategies
- Realization of cross-sectorial synergies for resource and energy efficient industry
- Geographical Information System (GIS) based analysis and visualization capabilities

Representational State Transfer system architecture is utilized in order to increase the performance of EPESUS software and improving its modular management. Moreover, data visualization works have been completed for assisting the decision support.

Unit processes are connected to each other with flows in EPESUS. The flows between the processes of a selected system model can be illustrated in terms of amounts and costs with Sankey diagrams. After entrance of required data with the aid of flows, the generated system models are ready to perform LCA.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

The desired system model and preferred impact categories should be selected in order to perform LCA. For the LCC of defined system model, economic parameters including currency, inflation rate, interest rate and whenever desired specific water and energy price rise rates should be identified. Furthermore, for LCC, the calculation period and annual production capacity of the related system model should be specified. According to these data entry, EPESUS calculates net present values and life cycle costs for the whole functional system or per functional unit.

EPESUS provides an evaluation and benchmarking analysis with other system models based on performed cost analysis and supports these analyses with appropriate visualizations consisting of graphics and tables. For a chosen system model, it is also possible to see the contribution of different cost components annually on a graphic. Moreover, annual cash flows for the selected time period according to calculated life cycle cost of the selected system model can be viewed.

Through the software platform, industrial symbiosis networks can be studied in terms of material, water, energy and knowledge networks. Additional novel analyses capabilities and especially visual representation of the network will help to assess indicators such as reciprocity, which assures collaboration is beneficial for all participants and centrality, which indicates company's position in the network.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

5 CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS GOOD PRACTICES

5.1 China's Use of Circular Economy Indicators

China consuming more raw materials than 34 countries of OECD and generates more waste than 28 countries of EU, has been taking action to promote the recirculation of waste materials through setting targets and adopting policies, financial measures and legislation for the last decade [106]. To transform from an ecologically and economically inefficient order, China adopted the concept of the CE as a national regulatory policy priority over the last decade leading to the Circular Economy Promotion Law of 2008. This law promotes the CE principle at three levels: individual firm level, the eco-industrial park level and the macro- or eco-city/eco-province level [107].

For an initial set of indicators, China turned to the European system described above for indicators in the four categories given in Figure 20.

Input category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Direct Material Input (DMI), corresponding to the materials used as direct input into the production process; ➔ Total Material Input (TMI), including both DMI and unused domestic extraction, and ➔ Total Material Requirement (TMR), including indirect material flows in addition to TMI
Consumption category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Domestic Material Consumption (DMC), including the total material requirements for domestic consumption ➔ Total Material Consumption (TMC), measuring the total amount of materials directly used in the economic system.
Balance category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Net Additions to Stock (NAS) that can be used to measure growth in the physical stocks of the economy ➔ Physical Trade Balance (PTB) represents the net inflow or outflow of physical materials.
Output category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Domestic Processed Output (DPO) measures all out flows of used materials

Figure 20 Initial set of CE indicators developed in China (adapted from [107])

However, it is recognised that the above indicators derived from material flow analysis have limitations such as data availability, deficiency in indicating environmental and health effects and failing to measure the decrease in consumption and waste generation. For these reasons an additional set of indicators given in Figure 21 is adopted by the Ministry of Environmental Protection, together with carbon emissions and ecological characteristics [107].

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Resource output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Output of main mineral resource ➔ Output of energy.
Resource consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Energy consumption per unit of GDP, energy consumption per added industrial value energy consumption per unit of product in key industrial sectors ➔ Water withdrawal per unit of GDP, water withdrawal per added industrial value, water consumption per unit product in key industrial sectors,
Integrated resource utilisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Recycling rate of industrial solid waste ➔ Safe treatment rate of domestic solid wastes, ➔ Industrial water reuse ratio and recycling rate of reclaimed municipal waste water ➔ Recycling rate of iron scrap, nonferrous metal, waste paper, plastic and rubber.
Waste disposal and pollutant emissions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Total amount of industrial solid waste for final disposal ➔ Total amount of sulphur dioxide emissions ➔ Total amount of industrial wastewater discharge and COD discharge.

Figure 21 China's additional CE indicators (adapted from [107])

Although overall resource consumption rose fivefold, with the efforts between 2005 to 2013, resource intensity (resources used per unit GDP) and waste intensity (waste per unit GDP), had improved by 34.7% and 46.5%, respectively, showing that resource consumption (of metal, water, energy and biomass) is decoupling from economic growth in relative terms. National Bureau of Statistics of China developed an index aggregating waste recycling and pollutant treatment rate to resource intensity and waste intensity. Circular economy development index increased by 38% between 2005 and 2013 [106].

Installation of eco-industrial parks are another crucial initiative for achieving China's circular economy targets with their advantages as close interaction among industries, shared infrastructure and centralised waste management. There are 33 eco-industrial parks, which create a synergy for industrial symbiosis among companies. Main contributions of these parks to circularity are reuse of wastewater, centralised heat networks promoting clean energy sources and efficient cascaded use of energy, and reuse and recycling of wastes to decrease resource consumption. [108]

5.2 Japan's Recycle-Oriented Society and Use of Indicators

Japan's first initiative for encouraging a circular economy was the adoption of the Law for Promotion of Effective Utilisation of Resources in 1991 which was followed by a Basic Law for Establishing a Material-cycling Society in 2000 and sector-specific legislation in subsequent years regarding end-of-life cars, packaging, home appliances, construction waste and food waste. As a result of this attempts, Japan accomplished a significant increase in recycling rates. As an example, recycling rate of PET bottles increased by 150% and unit cost of recycling decreased by 98% between 2000 to 2014. [107]

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Three main circular economy indicators monitored by Japan are resource productivity (GDP per tonne of resources used), material recycle rate (%) and the weight of waste for final disposal (tonnes). In Japan, indicators of societal efforts for circularity are also measured. These indicators are size of the market for rental and leasing of goods, results of surveys of consumer awareness and actions related to circularity. Generation of municipal waste per capita, industrial waste production and economic contribution of recycling are also monitored. [107]

Figure 22 Circular economy indicators monitored in Japan (adapted from [107])

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

6 POTENTIAL FOR REPLICATION UNDER CIRC-PACK PROJECT

6.1 Evaluation and Relevancy of Indicators to CIRC-PACK Project

6.1.1 Relevancy of Indicators to CIRC-PACK

Relevance of the indicators mentioned in Section 3 to CIRC-PACK value chain is evaluated based on expert judgement considering the following factors:

- Objectives of the CIRC-PACK project
- Expected impacts of the CIRC-PACK project
- Impacts of transition of plastics packaging value chain from linear to circular

The relevance matrix that classifies indicators as high, moderate and low relevance according to abovementioned criteria is given in Table 20 and details of this evaluation are given in the following discussions.

Table 20 Relevance matrix for studied indicators

Relevance matrix for studied indicators			
Indicator	High relevance	Moderate relevance	Low relevance
Environmental Indicators			
Raw material consumption, intensity, efficiency			
Total raw materials	VC		
Primary raw materials (renewable and non-renewable feedstock)	VC DC-A		
Secondary raw materials	VC DC-A		
Energy consumption, intensity, efficiency			
Total energy		VC	
Fossil fuels		DC-C	
Renewable energy sources			
Electricity			
Exergy consumption, intensity, efficiency			X
Water consumption, intensity, efficiency			
Total water			X
Surface and groundwater			
Rain water			

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE		Version: 1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423		Date: 31/8/17

Relevance matrix for studied indicators			
Indicator	High relevance	Moderate relevance	Low relevance
Reclaim water			
Greenhouse gas emissions Reported in CO ₂ -eq	VC DC-A DC-B DC-C		
Air emissions Pollutant emission Intensity of air pollutants	VC		
Wastewater Total wastewater generation Wastewater intensity Wastewater recycling rate Pollution load			x
Waste generation Total waste, hazardous and non-hazardous waste generation Waste intensity	VC DC-A DC-B DC-C		
Waste hierarchy Rate of recycling Rate of incineration (with and without energy recovery) Rate of landfilling	VC DC-A DC-B DC-C		
By-products and recyclables Efficiency of recycling processes Efficiency of valorisation	VC DC-A DC-B DC-C		
LCA Indicators			
GWP / Carbon Footprint	VC		
Cumulative Energy Demand	VC		
EMC	VC		
Abiotic Resource Depletion	VC		
Human Toxicity	VC		
Economic indicators			
Production volume		VC	
Turnover		VC	
Net added value	VC		
OPEX and CAPEX	VC DC-A DC-B		

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment	
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version: 1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date: 31/8/17

Relevance matrix for studied indicators			
Indicator	High relevance	Moderate relevance	Low relevance
	DC-C		
NPV	VC DC-A DC-B DC-C		
ROI and IRR		VC DC-A DC-B DC-C	
LCC	VC DC-A DC-B DC-C		
Social indicators			
Employment Job creation (% by sector)	VC		
Consumer End of life responsibility			X
Society Public commitment to sustainability issues (willingness to pay/ ability to pay) Technology development (TRL) Contribution to economic development	VC		
Value Chain Actors Supplier relationships	VC		
Circularity indicators			
Linear flow/ circular flow index	VC DC-A DC-B DC-C		
Product utility			X
Material circularity indicator	VC		
Resource productivity	VC		
Value-based resource efficiency	VC		
Resource duration/longevity		VC	

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Environmental Indicators

Resource Efficiency Indicators

- ✓ *Raw material consumption, intensity, efficiency (total, primary and secondary raw materials)*
 - Indicators regarding raw materials are highly relevant since CIRC-PACK project have specific objectives and impacts that addresses a reduction in the use of primary raw materials (fossil feedstock) and an increase in secondary raw material consumption:

“CIRC-PACK will seek and validate 100% new biodegradable materials, from renewable resources, non-competitive with human crops, for targeted applications along the plastic value chain, which will be cost competitive regarding current fossil based plastics. Indicators on raw material consumption, intensity and efficiency can be found in all sustainability indicator sets which points their importance in any sustainability assessment.”

“CIRC-PACK will trigger the utilization of recycled material as raw material and create closed-loop recycling flows and multi-sectorial cascade recycling process.”

“The environmental impact of CIRC-PACK will have a direct reduction of the oil demand used in the packaging manufacture increasing the efficiency of exploitation of secondary raw materials, resource efficiency and the raw materials savings.”
 - Absolute consumption, intensity and efficiency indicators are all applicable for plastic packaging value chain. Among these, efficiency indicators would be the most useful to monitor the improvements of transition of the value chain from linear to circular in terms of primary and secondary raw material uses.
 - While monitoring primary raw material efficiency, fossil and renewable feedstock can be considered separately to observe impact of the CIRC-PACK model in reduction of oil demand and dependence on fossil feedstock for plastic packaging production.
 - Secondary raw materials efficiency is a useful indicator to monitor the recycling of cellulose

- ✓ *Energy consumption, intensity, efficiency*
 - Although there is not a certain overall target of CIRC-PACK project to reduce the energy consumption, energy is a crucial parameter for sustainability assessment.
 - It is only mentioned in DC-C that energy consumption of the sterilization unit will be monitored.
 - Including energy indicators in CEIS metrics may also be useful if the energy profile (i.e. energy sources) of the region under discussion is considered.
 - Analysis of energy consumption can also be relevant in ETV (Environmental Technology Verification) process.
 - Indicators related to energy are considered of moderate relevance.

- ✓ *Exergy consumption, intensity, efficiency*

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

- Since energy is not a focus of CIRC-PACK project, exergy is considered as lowly relevant.

✓ *Water consumption, intensity, efficiency*

- Indicators regarding water are evaluated of low relevance since plastics sector is not a water intensive sector. Moreover, CIRC-PACK projects does not have a specific focus or target on water.

Waste and Emissions Indicators

✓ *Greenhouse gas emissions*

- CIRC-PACK project has focus on reduction of fossil feedstock and landfilling in parallel with EU targets which brings up the need for monitoring GHG emissions.

“Substantially improving the efficient use of resources in Europe, leading to significant reduction of adverse environmental impacts, including on climate change and to optimisation of production.”

“All these actions imply a direct impact in the environment, especially in terms of fossil raw materials consumption, GHG emissions and landfill occupation”

“CIRC-PACK will contribute to the Zero plastics to landfill by 2025 with 1.2 M tonnes of plastic landfilled per year in the medium term. If there are not developed measures as CIRC-PACK the reduction of the plastics to landfill will go slowly and it will finish in 2037 instead of 2025.”

- GHG emissions are conceived as of high relevance to CIRC-PACK project.

✓ *Air emissions*

- Emissions of volatile organic compounds and particulate matter are considered among key environmental issues in polymer sector.
- Since air emissions can be used as a baseline to compare conventional linear plastics packaging value chain and CIRC-PACK value chain, it can be considered as high importance.

✓ *Wastewater*

- Indicators regarding wastewater are conceived as lowly relevant since plastics sector is not a water intensive sector. Moreover, CIRC-PACK projects does not have a specific focus or target on wastewater.

✓ *Waste generation*

- CIRC-PACK has specific focus on waste generation:

“New materials and designs more easily recycled will be demonstrated to tackle the effective recycling of multicomponent and multilayer packaging, which are at the centre of the greatest concern regarding packaging recycling, and thus having a direct impact in the reduction of residual waste ending landfilled or incinerated.”

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

“As a result, new materials, combinations and formulations selection and subsequent design of primary, secondary and tertiary packaging will be outcomes of the project, in view of a net reduction in the final waste produced.”

- Therefore, indicators regarding waste generation are evaluated as highly relevant.
- ✓ *Waste hierarchy*
 - CIRC-PACK has specific targets to promote waste hierarchy:

“CIRC-PACK boosts the waste hierarchy to maximize recovery and reduce waste focusing on eco-design of innovative products. This will help to move to a ‘circular economy model, seeking to avoid waste generation and to use waste as a resource.”
 - Waste hierarchy indicators are conceived as of high relevance to CIRC-PACK value chain and demo cases in particular.
- ✓ *By-products and recyclables*
 - CIRC-PACK project has specific focus on recycling efficiency, especially in Demo Cases A and B. Therefore, these are considered as highly relevant.

LCA Indicators

- So far, global warming potential (or carbon footprint), cumulative energy demand, human toxicity, fossil depletion and EMC stands out as the most relevant indicators on the impact assessment part.
- The most relevant LCA indicators will be selected during the LCA study in an iterative manner.
- Life cycle inventory phase of the LCA will contribute to estimation of many basic environmental indicators including consumption and waste generation related ones.

Economic Indicators

Production volume, turnover value and net added value provides meaningful and comparable information when used for normalization. They are used to calculate intensity indicators, which are also called specific indicators that provide a basis for comparison between different system parameters sharing a common denominator. Units for these indicators always contain the unit of what is being measured and the unit of item used for normalization, i.e. mass/mass, mass/monetary value, energy/mass, volume/monetary value etc.

- ✓ *Production volume*
 - Production volume is one of the parameters that are monitored in every industrial facility or sector. Not only it is the basis for the economic income to be gained by the company, it also gives an indication on capacity utilization in the plant or sector.
 - Production volume can be used to calculate normalized values (or intensity indicators) sharing a common denominator which enables benchmarking between the baseline and the change.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

- Intensity indicators calculated based on production volume can also be used to make an assessment for a production process which may be the case for assessment of Demo Cases in CIRC-PACK project. Therefore, this indicator is classified under moderate relevance.
- ✓ *Turnover*
 - Turnover can be used to calculate normalized values (or intensity indicators) sharing a common denominator which enables benchmarking between the baseline and the change.
 - Intensity indicators calculated based on turnover can also be used to make an assessment for a production process which may be the case for assessment of Demo Cases in CIRC-PACK project. Therefore, this indicator is classified under moderate relevance.
- ✓ *Net added value*
 - Net added value can be used to calculate normalized values (or intensity indicators) sharing a common denominator which enables benchmarking between the baseline and the change.
 - Intensity indicators calculated based on net added value can also be used to make an assessment for a production process which may be the case for assessment of Demo Cases in CIRC-PACK project. Therefore, this indicator is classified under moderate relevance.
 - Another interesting discussion on net added value would be utilizing this parameter to monitor the economic impact of upcycling targeted by installing the CIRC-PACK value chain.
 - This indicator is considered as highly relevant for CEIS metrics to be developed.
- ✓ *OPEX and CAPEX*
 - Considering the current linear value chain as business as usual, OPEX of business as usual scenario can be compared to CAPEX + OPEX of interventions of CIRC-PACK model. Due to added investment required for installing a circular value chain, this comparison may result in an unfair situation. This consideration also promotes the use of LCC as the primary economic indicator since it covers added values, avoided burdens and externalized environmental costs which will lead a fairer comparison in favour of circularity.
 - OPEX and CAPEX can also be used to monitor Demo Cases or certain parts of the value chain.
 - OPEX and CAPEX are considered as highly relevant for CEIS metrics to be developed.
- ✓ *NPV*
 - NPV is the main indicator for LCC (in this case WLC) which is achieved by discounting all costs and benefits during the scope of the system to the present.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

- NPV is the major economic indicator that can be used to demonstrate the economic advantages of transition of plastic packaging value chain from linear to circular. Therefore, it is considered as highly relevant.
- ✓ *ROI and IRR*
 - Return on Investment and Internal Rate of Return on Investments are both more relevant for a decision on investment. However, they can still provide valuable information if ROI and IRR analysis can be done for necessary investment on preservation of environmental quality with the new circular value chain.
 - Therefore, ROI and IPP are evaluated as moderately relevant for CEIS metrics.
- ✓ *LCC*
 - In order to obtain investment on preservation of environmental quality and burdens on different stakeholder groups, the whole life cycle over the value chain need to be taken into consideration in order to reveal the hidden costs and environmental externalities.
 - Life cycle cost or rather whole life cost indicator fulfils this aim and should be preferred over basic environmental indicators. Therefore, LCC is considered as highly relevant.

Social Indicators

- ✓ *Job creation:*
 - Since it is one of the main expected impacts of the project, it is classified as high relevance indicator.
 - For monitoring the impacts of CIRC-PACK high / intermediate /low skill job creation may be discussed.
 - Moreover, contribution to local employment can also be considered.
- ✓ *End of life responsibility*
 - Since improvements of CIRC-PACK will have limited influence on a change in end of life responsibility of the consumers, it is considered as lowly relevant.
- ✓ *Public commitment to sustainability issues (willingness to pay/ ability to pay)*
 - Although CIRC-PACK has not a specific target to increase public commitment to sustainability, it can be interesting to monitor this indicator. Therefore, it is conceived under high relevance.
- ✓ *Technology development*
 - CIRC-PACK has specific focus on technology development:

“Long term impacts of CIRC-PACK: Contribution to improving the innovation capacity and the integration of new knowledge

CIRC-PACK demonstrates and validates technological and non-technological innovations, described in the section 1, the project will achieve numerous

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

developments up the TRL chain in order to bridge the innovation gap that is currently preventing them from making it from laboratory validation to industrial scale. Indeed, some of the systems to be piloted in CIRC-PACK, such as the polymerization process are new technologies that, once demonstrated by the project, open up a pathway to their commercialisation. This brings a new opportunity for a technology manufacture industry to develop around the outputs of CIRC-PACK.”

- Therefore, Technology Development is conceived as of high relevance.
- ✓ *Contribution to economic development*
 - Since economic benefits gained by CIRC-PACK value chain will also promote the economic development of the society, it is considered as highly relevant.
- ✓ *Supplier relationships*
 - CIRC-PACK value chain creates a synergy between several actors in the value chain promoting the supplier relationships.
 - Therefore, this indicator is considered as of high relevance.

Circularity Indicators

- ✓ *Linear flow / circular flow index*
 - CIRC-PACK project has specific objectives to decrease virgin feedstock consumption and to increase the recyclability of the plastic packaging and the recycling efficiency.
 - As plastics are designed and produced with increased recyclability -especially if upcycling is achieved-, the use of virgin feedstock will be reduced. Since CIRC-PACK chain aims to reduce virgin feedstock, linear flow index will be decreased as well indicating an improvement as a result of circularity.
 - Moreover, CIRC-PACK innovations include improvement in sorting and recycling processes which will yield in a decrease in the amount of unrecoverable waste generated in recycling process as well as when producing recycled feedstock. This can also be monitored by linear flow index.
 - Therefore, linear flow index is highly relevant with CIRC-PACK value chain and demo cases.
- ✓ *Product Utility*
 - Utility is based on a product's lifetime and function. Lifetime and function of a packaging material finishes when the product (i.e., the product inside the packaging material) is bought and used. This characteristic of the packaging material makes product utility inapplicable and irrelevant to consider for assessing CIRC-PACK value chain. Therefore, it is considered as of low relevance.
 - On the other hand, if the packaging material improves the product life time (i.e., the expire date of the packed product) compared to the average, product utility can be considered as an indicator that enhances the circularity. If the innovative packaging materials that will be developed under CIRC-PACK, have a positive impact on the

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

expiration date of the product, then this indicator may be thought under moderately relevant indicators.

✓ *Material Circularity Indicator*

- Material circularity indicator is derived from linear flow index and product utility. Although product utility is not so applicable, since linear flow index linear impact MCI, MCI is also considered as highly relevant.
- MCI is a product based indicator and can be aggregated for a product range of a company. Therefore, there may be a need to modify MCI to be used based on the plastics packaging value chain.

✓ *Resource Productivity*

- Resource productivity is generally used in a national/regional context. However, the idea behind it can be useful to monitor the circularity improvements in a value chain as monetary value over consumed resources.
- Since, like any circularity initiative, CIRC-PACK has specific targets to reduce resource consumption, resource productivity can be adapted and used for assessment of CIRC-PACK value chain. Comparison of linear and circular value chains in terms of resource productivity will result in favour of circular ones even if the market value remains the same.
- Resource productivity is considered as highly relevant with CIRC-PACK.

✓ *Value-based Resource Efficiency*

- This indicator adds social and environmental aspects to the idea of Resource Productivity. It includes not only the monetary value gained but also economic value of social and environmental benefits.
- Therefore, using such an indicator for assessment of CIRC-PACK value chain will promote circularity by revealing the positive social and environmental impacts.
- Although monetarizing social and environmental impacts can be compelling, it can be a very relevant indicator if it can be adapted to plastic packaging value chain.

✓ *Resource Duration /Longevity*

- Resource duration indicates the retention of a material within a product system, where greater retention means the use of the resource is maximised.
- It is considered as moderately relevant to CIRC-PACK since it also covers refurbishment which is not applicable to packaging materials.
- This indicator can be highly relevant if it is adapted to CIRC-PACK value chain by removing refurbishment and taking down-cycling into consideration.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

6.1.2 Evaluation of Indicators

The RACER and SMART criteria is recommended to be utilized to assess the quality of indicators while carrying out indicator-based assessments. There are already examples of RACER and SMART criteria evaluation in the literature for a variety of indicators including resource efficiency indicators [109][110][111].

SMART criteria is operational and specific to objectives of the study. Therefore, it is suggested to integrate the evaluation according to SMART criteria to the process of indicator selection, which is expected to be iterative

For RACER criteria, which is more policy related, the evaluation process is initiated by identifying sub-criteria under each RACER criteria set and conducting the assessment of indicators based on these sub-criteria. Later a qualitative analysis (high conformity – green, medium conformity – yellow, low conformity – red) or a basic quantitative analysis of scoring based on expert judgement can be carried out. Examples of these sub-criteria are provided in Annex.

Previous RACER assessment of general indicator groups relevant to CIRC-PACK project revealed following:

R- Relevance

- | | |
|-------------------------------|---|
| <i>Policy relevance</i> | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material use, energy consumption, water use are all scored high under this criterion. • Environmental impact oriented indicators allow monitoring the different impacts related to material, energy, water and land use thus is related to the key policy objectives as formulated in several EU resource policies, most notably the Resource Strategy and the Resource Efficiency Flagship. However, impact indicators partially fulfil this criterion with the exception of the indicators of GHG emission, which are already being used in EU climate policies. |
| <i>Sensitiveness</i> | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The sensitiveness of the indicators for both resource use- and impact-oriented indicators relate closely to the availability of data. • This criterion should be assessed under Task 2.2 after data requirements for each indicator is identified. |
| <i>Rebound effects</i> | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A complete fulfilment of this criterion was allocated to those indicators, which take a consumption-perspective. • On the impact side, while some indicators including carbon footprint can monitor all rebound effects related to consumption, territorial GHG emissions for instance, cannot fully capture the rebound effects. |
| <i>Past/future trends and</i> | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The availability of time series for the past is limited to a few indicators on both resource use and environmental impact side. |

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

early warning

- Future trends are identified though with a level of uncertainty for energy and material consumption scenarios. Except for the GHG emissions, which are used in climate modelling, all environmental impact indicators received a medium score.
- Impact oriented indicators fulfil early warning criterion. The examples include energy consumption indicators serving as early-warning indicators for climate change. Other resource use indicators, such as the water consumption or land use indicators need to be combined with environmental threshold values, in order to serve as early warning indicators for policy makers.

A - accepted

*Policy makers,
statistics,
business,
academia,
civil society*

- Most of the resource use-oriented indicators in the basket are widely accepted by policy makers as informing about the different aspects of EU resource use. However, quality, appropriateness, and actuality of life-cycle data will be crucial for its future acceptance.
- Statistical offices being main data provider for almost all resource use-oriented indicators on the national and EU level, acceptance by statistical institutions is generally very high. The life cycle indicators rely on data, which are gathered outside statistics so for these acceptance by statistics is low.
- Companies can benefit from measuring the resource use to improve their efficiency. Energy and raw material consumption as well as GHG emissions are among widely accepted indicators. Information on carbon emissions allocable to products are also drawing attention on the consumer side.
- Acceptance of the suggested indicators in the academic world is generally very high and academic institutions played a key role in further developing the methodologies and data sets of the various resource use indicators. Acceptance of impact indicators vary within academia as the methodologies are still under development.
- Most of the impact indicators are not (yet) widely used by civil society organisations.
- The two efficiency indicators (“CO₂ emission intensity” and “GHG emission intensity”) show a high level of acceptance, but some potential for improvements with regard to their credibility—the transparency and harmonization of the calculation methodology.
- Air emission intensity and recycling rates also show high acceptance among stakeholders.

C- credible

*Unambiguous
results and
transparency*

- Most of the resource use-oriented indicators provide unambiguous results and a clear message. On the other hand, several of the impact indicators require a careful interpretation of results; this criterion is therefore only partly fulfilled for most of them.
- Clear specifications of the underlying methodologies are available for

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

resource use-oriented indicators thus criterion of transparency is fulfilled. However, impact-oriented indicators, life cycle indicators in particular may rely heavily on life cycle inventory data, which are not freely available and fully documented, limiting their transparency.

E- easy

Availability of data to calculate indicators and calculated indicators

- Limited transparency of life cycle inventories also causes the impact-oriented indicators to score lower than resource use-indicators whose underlying data is more available.
- Work has to be invested in the improvement of data availability and quality of “CO₂ emission intensity” and “GHG emission intensity” indicators, as well as the availability of the calculated indicators and their accordance with statistical standards.

Technical feasibility

- Most of the indicators related to environmental impacts of domestic resource use can be calculated without any significant knowledge in computer programming or modelling, as the data from the original sources do not require major transformation.
- Most of the life cycle indicators require a substantial technical knowledge for their calculation and specific LCA software and knowledge how to use them properly.
- Recycling rates and air emission intensity score high with regard to their easiness (availability of data and data series, etc.).

R- robust

Data quality and geographic scale

- Physical production and consumption volumes necessary to calculate resource use -oriented indicators are available in good quality.
- LCA related data including the inventory and impact factors are often prone to uncertainties and subject to variety on the geographic and temporal basis.
- Data for most indicators are available for all EU-27 countries plus a number of non-EU countries, if taken from an international data source. Data of the indicators are in several cases not yet available for all EU countries.

Level of aggregation and reproducibility

- This criterion is fulfilled by all indicators in the basket, as all indicators can be used either as an aggregated number on the economy-wide level, or be disaggregated by different sub-categories or economic sectors, in order to be closer linked to actual policy making.
- One key problem related to the material impact indicators is that LCA impact factors are only available for single products, which makes it difficult to apply them for macro assessments.
- Full reproducibility of results is only ensured for a limited number of indicators. Reproducibility of results is limited, as the methodologies for most indicators are not yet harmonised.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

- Burden shifting*
- The indicators for the category of “Carbon” contain territorial indicators (i.e. CO₂ and GHG emissions and their respective intensities), life cycle based indicators (i.e. Carbon footprint). The territorial indicators by definition cover all emissions of the whole economy within that territory. This means that these indicators cover rebound effects but since they do not take a life cycle approach, they are only partly robust against burden shifting i.e. the burden shifting within the territory. The robustness against burden shifting is the main property of the Carbon Footprint indicator.

6.1.3 Recommendations for Further Studies on Indicators

After reviewing all the indicators, some gaps for indicators to represent and monitor the improvements targeted with transition to CIRC-PACK value chain is identified. Below discussion reveals additional indicators that can be considered in CEIS metrics to be developed.

✓ *Recycling index*

- Recycling rate is based on a single material stream or a single product and may be insufficient for assessing the recycling targets of the CIRC-PACK value chain, which is multi-sectorial and focuses on more than one material stream.
- DC-B aims the design of new packaging that do not limit the recyclability of other material (paper).
- DC-C focuses on multi-sectorial products and assesses their recyclability.
- For these reasons, developing a recycling index specific to CIRC-PACK value chain would be beneficial.

✓ *Biodegradability*

- In accordance with ISO 17556, biodegradability refers to materials able to be breakdown by microorganisms in the presence of oxygen into carbon dioxide, water and mineral salts of any other elements present (mineralization) plus new biomass.
- Production of biodegradable plastics is one of the main objectives of the project and biodegradability test will be performed for produced packaging materials.
- Therefore, integrating biodegradability into CEIS metrics would be meaningful to monitor the benefits of CIRC-PACK value chain.
- Moreover, marine biodegradability and soil biodegradability can be assessed separately.

✓ *Compostability*

- In accordance with EN 13432, compostability refers to materials able to biodegrade in a controlled composting process through the action of naturally occurring microorganisms that yields in CO₂, water, inorganic compounds and biomass.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

- Since the CIRC-PACK project has specific objectives regarding the compostability of developed plastics, it would be useful to monitor compostability as an indicator.
- ✓ *Up-cycling / down-cycling rate*
 - A recycling process that reduces the quality and economic value of a material or product is often described as down-cycling. Likewise, upcycling is used to define a recycling process that increases the quality and economic value of a material or product. [3]
 - CIRC-PACK has specific objectives for the quality of the recycled material:
 - “In addition, new in-process and in real-time metering system will be applied to monitor the quality of recovered plastic processes, at different stages of the recovery process, avoiding final product batch wastage, enabling that 30% of the recovered plastic can be used in higher quality applications compared to current practices.”*
 - Therefore, it would be useful to have a specific definition of upcycling and down-cycling for CIRC-PACK value chain and this parameter can be included in CEIS metrics as an indicator.
- ✓ *Sorting efficiency*
 - One of the innovations targeted by CIRC-PACK project is the improvement of sorting efficiency. Therefore, it can be useful to monitor the improvements achieved.

6.2 Evaluation of Assessment Methodologies and Applicability to CIRC-PACK

Assessment methodologies covered in Section 2 (i.e., value chain assessment, life cycle approach and circular economy assessment) are discussed below in terms of their applicability CIRC-PACK project.

Value Chain Analysis

Principles of value chain analysis approach can be a useful for assessing CIRC-PACK value chain. Identifying the key players in the value chain (which has already been done for CIRC-PACK) enables clarification of input/output relationships between different actors.

Identification of monetary value added (i.e., the difference in the price of a material, mid-product or product between the stages of the value chain) at each step of the value chain allows to see the benefits added by each step or each value chain actor. Moreover, the added value concept, which is conventionally the monetary value, can be extended to environmental or socio-economic value added. For example, for CIRC-PACK value chain, jobs created or the reduction in the resource use at each value chain step may give an important insight of the benefit or added value of the innovations in each demo case.

Since CIRC-PACK project aims to develop an assessment methodology, which will have the indicators in the core of the methodology, selection of indicators is a crucial step. Although

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

value chain analysis suggests the evaluation of indicators individually at each value chain step, the methodology developed in CEIS will probably have some product based indicators as well as the indicators covering the whole value chain.

Life Cycle Approach

Life cycle thinking includes considerations of the economic, environmental and social impacts (or risks) of a product (or a process) within the sense of covering all life cycle steps from “cradle to grave” starting from the extraction of natural resources to the final disposal of the product along with any material recycling, energy recovery, reuse that may occur prior to ultimate disposition. Considering the CIRC-PACK objectives and system boundaries, the “cradle to grave” should be improved to a more inclusive approach as “cradle to cradle” as it is more compatible with the circular economy principles, such as “waste as a feedstock”. Therefore, CEIS methodology to be developed for circularity assessment of CIRC-PACK products and value chain should be based on cradle-to-cradle approach.

The scope of the upcoming tasks of CIRC-PACK clearly state that the CEIS will also include indicators based on life-cycle methodology (LCA and LCC), for the evaluation of the environmental and economic impact. Relevant impact categories for LCA and cost items including end-of-life and hidden environmental costs will be selected over the entire value chain. During this selection, not only demo specific conditions will be observed but also interactions between demo cases will be taken into account for integration purposes. Thus, CEIS should include an LCA, LCC analysis enabling scenario-based assessments addressing the significant impacts of the packaging plastics value chain stages and overall CIRC-PACK system.

Circular Economy Assessment

The framework developed by Elia et. al. (2016), summarized in Section 2.4, suggests circular economy to be evaluated and measured in a four level approach. These four levels and their possible application to CIRC-PACK project are discussed below.

Processes to monitor

- Processes to monitor includes the value chain steps from design to end-of-life.
- Identification of system boundary and the processes needed to be monitored within CIRC-PACK value chain and Demo Cases will be a relevant starting point.

Actions involved

- Actions involved are the building blocks for supporting the adoption of circular economy.
- Those actions can be derived from Demo Cases specific to CIRC-PACK project:
 - Decoupling plastics from fossil feedstock by using alternative renewable feedstock.
 - Creation of innovative formats and testing materials that improve recyclability and the end-of-life scenario
 - Creation of an effective after-use plastic economy by means of multi-sectorial cascaded approaching

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Requirements to be measured

- Requirements to be measured can be considered as the targets and objectives of the project corresponding to one or more measurable indicator.
- These can be listed specific to CIRC-PACK project as:
 - Reducing the use of fossil feedstock for plastic packaging production
 - Reducing CO₂ emissions
 - Increasing the recyclability of certain plastic packaging types
 - Increasing the share of bio-based and biodegradable products

Implementation levels

- Implementation levels in the framework are macro level (from cities to nations); the meso level (eco-industrial parks) and the micro level (single companies or customers).
- Assessment of circularity in CIRC-PACK can be performed at different levels such as company/individual value chain step or the plastic packaging value chain as a whole. Furthermore, assessment in larger scale is also targeted in WP 6 of the project at city, nation or regional level.
- The discussion on the implementation levels can be useful and meaningful in selection of appropriate methodology to assess circularity of CIRC-PACK value chain.

6.3 Evaluation of Decision Support Tools

In order to support the users/decision makers along the value chain to assess the impacts of CIRC-PACK value chain in terms of circularity improvements via monitoring the proposed indicators in CEIS metrics, a tool is planned to be developed in Task 2.5. Although the details and scope of the tool will be identified after CEIS metrics is developed, reviewing available decision support tools may provide useful insight for further discussions. For this purpose, the table below summarises and compares the decision support tools covered in Section 4 by providing short descriptions, platform supports, type of inputs and outputs (as qualitative/quantitative) and development statuses keeping in mind that all have different scopes and objectives.

Table 21 Decision Support Tools' Characteristics and Comparisons (Adapted from [7])

Decision Support Tools' Characteristics and Comparisons					
Tool	Description	Platform Support	Inputs	Outputs	Status
Circular Economy Toolkit (CET)	An assessment tool to identify potential improvement of products circularity	Dynamic Webpage	33 trinary-based questions related to 7 life cycle stages	Qualitative: Improvement potential at level 3 (high/medium/low) for every subcategory	Developed

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE		Version: 1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423		Date: 31/8/17

Decision Support Tools' Characteristics and Comparisons					
Tool	Description	Platform Support	Inputs	Outputs	Status
Material Circular Indicator (MCI)	A tool to support companies to measure their transition towards circularity	Excel Spreadsheet	Different percentages (reused, recycling) about material origin (feedstock) and destination (end-of-use)	Quantitative: Gives an single score between 0 and 1 where higher values indicate a higher circularity	Developed
Circular Economy Indicator Prototype (CEIP)	A decision support tool aiming to evaluate products circularity performance	Excel Spreadsheet	15 weighted questions divided into five life cycle stages	Quantitative: Gives an overall % score and a spider diagram showing aggregated score for each life cycle stage	Developed
Resource Conservative Manufacturing (RESCOM)	A decision support tool to provide circularity evaluation and design, life cycle management and material information management	Software package	Potential mass and value flows along the complex product chain and business model	Quantitative and Qualitative: Gives single scores for every life cycle stages and business models, simulation outputs, forecasting results and planning guidance	Under development
Eco-Industrial Park Environmental Support System (EPESUS)	EPESUS is a powerful tool for indicator based sustainability assessment with real time and spatial big data analysis capabilities	Software package	Material and energy flows throughout the life cycle processes of products	Quantitative: LCA, LCC results as well as GIS based Spatial Analysis Results, Scenario Comparison for decision support	Developed

Although the DSTs summarized above can both assess the circularity, they have different properties and functionalities in their processes. Assessing circularity of a value chain is quite complex to resolve, so that it is suggested to set the baseline for desired outputs and related methodological requirements in terms of CIRC-PACK system boundaries and objectives. Those decisions will be made in Task 2.5 in detail but some conceptual suggestions to aid further studies on the tool to be developed is given below:

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

*Baseline for the assessment
(i.e., product/company/ value
chain/ industrial symbiosis)*

- Both product and value chain level assessment should be covered.
- Individual DC evaluation should also be possible as the subsystems of the CIRC-PACK is expected to be circular as well
- The material input-output interactions between value chain actors should be well illustrated and assessed.

*Adaptive and Flexible
(for different type of products/
product chains)*

- Considering the tool is to be developed only for CIRC-PACK project, there is no significant need for adaptability to other value chains or products
- The tool should be able to cover all the products (or the products family) that are either produced or consumed in the CIRC-PACK value chain
- The tool should be flexible in terms of input and output material streams since multi sectorial wastes will be utilized

Ease of use

- The ease of use of the tool should be designed according to targeted user profile: decision makers, manufacturers, experts

Life cycle thinking

- In order to assess circularity properly on plastics value chain, it is highly important and relevant to use the life cycle thinking in combination with the other assessment methodologies
- The tool should be in strong harmony with LCA, LCC, S-LCA approaches to be able to monitor CEIS indicators properly
- Developed tool should enable cradle-to-cradle approach which enables a comprehensive circularity assessment in the value chain

Indicator based assessment

- The tool should enable the indicator based assessment to monitor the product(s) and value chain in line with the CEIS metrics.
- If CEIS methodology includes any aggregated indicators and indices, the tool should also be capable of handling those.

*Scenario based assessment for
circularity improvement*

- Considering the CIRC-PACK methodology and objectives, CEIS should be highly skilled with the capability to work on different scenarios or sub-systems
- Accordingly, CEIS should be equipped with strong illustrative design in order to differentiate the outputs after scenario based assessments

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

The aim of this report is to provide the state-of-the-art of the circularity assessment. For this purpose, a comprehensive literature review is made regarding relevant assessment methodologies, sustainability and circularity indicators and decision support tools and they all evaluated in terms of their applicability to CIRC-PACK.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Value chain analysis, life cycle approach and circular economy assessment is covered and core principles of CEIS methodology. Value chain analysis brings a clear identification of each step/actor in the chain and its added value which is very crucial for a complex and multi-sectorial system as CIRC-PACK. Life cycle thinking should definitely be included in the methodology by improving the approach from cradle-to-grave to cradle-to-cradle which is more compatible with the concept of circular economy. Furthermore, it may be useful to set a framework specific to circularity assessment of CIRC-PACK by identifying processes to monitor, involved actors, requirements to be measured and implementation level.

Indicators are embraced under three pillars of sustainability (environmental, economic and social) and circularity. While determining the relevancy level of indicators to CIRC-PACK CEIS methodology, expert decisions are made considering the objectives and expected impacts of CIRC-PACK project as well as foreseen impacts of transition of plastics packaging value chain from linear to circular.

In order to guide the efforts in Task 2.2 in terms of indicators selection, SMART and RACER criteria are explained and especially the latter, which is more policy related, is evaluated in details regarding the general indicator groups relevant to CIRC-PACK. Based on previous and extensive RACER evaluation on resource efficiency indicators, in particular the consumption based basic environmental indicators are determined to score high with respect to the RACER criteria. The emission based indicators (waste generation, recycling etc.) were not analysed as detailed as consumption based indicators, however, they are crucial for the CIRC-PACK value chain assessment and will be utilized as part of CEIS. Life cycle indicators have some shortcomings in terms of RACER evaluation especially in terms of data availability, technical feasibility and transparency. LCA methodologies are still advancing and life cycle thinking is an indispensable part of the value chain assessment approach of CIRC-PACK. Furthermore, life cycle indicators are the only group of indicators that are able to reveal the burden shifting.

The indicators reviewed under D2.1 are extensive in terms of their coverage. Depending on the system boundary definition to be made under Task 2.2, they can be utilized to assess production systems on company and product basis, throughout complete value chains or even broader to assess the upscaling potential of CIRC-PACK solutions.

The functional unit definition for LCA and LCC studies will also provide a basis for the scope of the indicator assessment. The geographic coverage will also be decided according to needs of assessment. If the functional unit is set for the entire value chain, then the primary data collected

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

(data related to basic environmental indicators) should cover all the processes within the value chain and this data should be normalized by the functional unit. Normalization can also be carried out using the basic economic indicators such as net value added. If the normalization for an indicator is done in terms of capacity or product quantity, the assessment can be made for a production process. If the normalization is done over turnover, it is possible carry out the evaluation at company level. When we do the normalization for net added value, we can extend out scope to value chains.

Five decision support tools with varying objectives and scopes are reviewed and compared to give an insight of the existing tools for circularity assessment. Although the context of the tool that will be composed under Task 2.5 will be made certain following the development of CEIS metrics, conceptual suggestions are made in terms of its baseline, flexibility, ease of use and coverage.

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

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	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

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	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version:	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

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	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

ANNEX: RACER ASSESSMENT CRITERIA AND SUB-CRITERIA EXPLAINED

RACER criteria for assessment of resource efficiency indicators (Resource use-oriented and environmental impact-oriented indicators) [109] are presented in the below table:

RACER criteria for assessment of resource efficiency indicators	
RACER Criterion	Sub-criteria
R - Relevant	Policy support for resource policies
	Policy support for other policies
	Sensitiveness
	Rebound effects
	Past trends
	Future trends
	Early warning
A - Accepted	Policy makers
	Statistics
	Business/industry
	Academia
C- Credible	Civil society
	Unambiguous results
E - Easy	Transparency
	Availability of data to calculate the indicator
	Availability of the calculated indicator
R - Robust	Technical feasibility
	Data quality
	Level of aggregation of data
	Reproducibility
	Geographical scale
	Burden shifting

List of sub-criteria for RACER evaluation of resource efficiency indicators and qualitative assessment (G-Green, Y-Yellow, R-Red) are presented in the below table [111]:

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

List of sub-criteria for RACER evaluation of resource efficiency indicators and qualitative			
	RACER Criterion	Underlying question	Specification of criterion
R - Relevant	Levels of economic activity	Is the indicator available for the relevant levels of economic activity, i.e. countries and sectors?	Data available on the national and sectorial level? (G) Is the indicator available for the relevant levels of economic activity, i.e. countries and sectors? (Y) Data are not available on either of the two levels (R)
	Disaggregation of resource components	Does the indicator allow disaggregation of environmental information in the required detail?	The indicator can be used as an aggregated indicator or highly disaggregated into its components to allow specific assessments (G) The indicator can be used as an aggregated indicator and be disaggregated into major components (Y) The indicator is only available as an aggregated number and cannot be detailed for environmental analyses (R)
	Rebound effects	Does the indicator capture rebound effects?	The indicator covers the whole economy and thus captures possible rebound effects on the macro level (G) The indicator covers parts of the whole economy (e.g. all manufacturing industries) and thus partly captures rebound effects (Y) The indicator focuses on one specific issue (e.g. one sector, one resource category) and disregards rebound effects on the macro level (R)
	Global perspective/Burden shifting	Is the indicator robust against burden shifting from one country/region to another?	The indicator takes a full life- cycle perspective and is thus robust against shifts between countries (G) The indicator includes direct trade (e.g. DMC), but no life- cycle perspective and thus is robust against outsourcing only to a limited extent (Y) The indicator is fully territorial and thus outsourcing improves the apparent performance of countries (R)
	Linkage to issues as scarcity and env. impact	Does the indicator link resource use and issues such as scarcity or environmental impact	The indicator directly addresses issues such as scarcity or environmental impacts (G) The indicator focuses on resource use but allows for a link with issues such as scarcity or environmental impacts (Y) The indicator does not allow for a link with issues such as scarcity or environmental impacts (R)
Accente	Policy makers	Is the indicator accepted by European policy makers?	The indicator is accepted and used by policy makers (G) The indicator is known by policy makers, but not actively used (Y) The indicators is not considered relevant by policy makers (R)

Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
Author:	EKODENGE	Version	1
Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	Statistics	Is the indicator accepted by statisticians?	The indicator is accepted and used by statisticians (G) The indicator is known by statisticians, but not actively used (Y) The indicators is not considered relevant by statisticians (R)
	Business	Is the indicator accepted by representatives from business?	The indicator is accepted and used by business (G) The indicator is known by business, but not actively used (Y) The indicators is not considered relevant by business (R)
	Academia	Is the indicator accepted by academic institutions?	The indicator is accepted and used by academia (G) The indicator is known by academia, but not actively used (Y) The indicators is not considered relevant by academia (R)
	Civil society	Is the indicator accepted civil society organisations?	The indicator is accepted and used by civil society (G) The indicator is known by civil society, but not actively used (Y) The indicators is not considered relevant by civil society (R)
C- Credible	Transparency of methodology	Are clear specifications of the underlying methodology available (e.g. protocols, standards, technical descriptions), and can the results be easily reproduced?	Full methodological specifications are available in scientifically standardised format (G) Methodological specifications are available, but the results cannot be easily reproduced. (Y) No (detailed) methodological specifications are available (R)
	Harmonisation of methodology	Is the underlying methodology harmonised?	Only one methodology exists and is fully harmonised on the international level. (G) A few methodological "schools" exist for calculating the indicator (e.g. LCA vs. input- output analysis for upstream flows) in parallel. No general consent is reached on which is the best method to apply. (Y) The method available is not approved in a scientifically standardized format (R)
E - Easy	Availability of data to calculate the indicator	How easily can data be obtained to calculate the indicator?	Data is available for free (e.g. internet download) in appropriate formats (e.g. Excel spread sheets; data base formats; vector formats) without restrictions (G) Data is available (either in appropriate formats (see above) or formats like pdf or hard copies), but licence systems are applied (Y) Data is not available for third users (R)
	Availability of the calculated indicator	How easily can the calculated indicator be obtained for various users?	The indicator is available for free (e.g. internet download) in appropriate formats (e.g. Excel spread sheets; data base formats; vector formats) without restrictions (G) The indicators is available (either in appropriate formats (see above) or formats like pdf or hard copies), but licence systems are applied (Y) The indicator is not available for third users (R)

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	Time series	Do time series exist? (and thus allow analysis of historical trends as well as provide input for models of future scenarios)	Data are available for a time series of 10 years or more (or 10 specific years in a longer time period) (G) Data are available for a time period of less than 10 years (or less than 10 specific years in a longer time period) (Y) Data are only available for one or two points in time (R)
	Technical feasibility	Can the indicator be calculated using standard software or does its calculation require specific programmes and technical expertise?	The indicator can be calculated in simple spread sheets without any specific software or specific technical skills (G) The indicator calculation requires the use of specific programmes (e.g. LCA software), but the programmes have practical user interfaces (Y) Calculation of the indicator requires mathematical programming skills (e.g. MRIO calculations undertaken with Matlab or similar software) (R)
R - Robust	Data quality	How solid is the data quality of the basic data underlying the indicator?	The underlying data is published by national or international (e.g. Eurostat) statistical institutions or international organisations (e.g. UN data units, OECD data units) (G) The underlying data is published by academic institutions or other organisations (e.g. business, NGOs, etc.) (Y) The underlying data stems from unknown sources or cannot be judged regarding its quality (R)
	Accordance with official statistical/accounting standards	Are the used data and the methodology in accordance with official statistical/accounting standards?	The used data and the methodology are in accordance with official statistical/accounting standards (G) Either used data or the methodology are in accordance with official statistical/accounting standards, but differences can be detected in specific aspects.(Y) The used data and the methodology are not in accordance with official statistical/accounting standards (R)
	Share of estimated data	Are the used data to a large extent real or estimated?	Only empirical data from statistical sources or own data compilations are used. (G) The used data are to a large extent real. (Y) The data are mainly estimated via estimation procedures or modelling.(R)

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

Another list of subcriteria developed under ERA-NET SKIP Project EIPOT “Development of a methodology for the assessment of global environmental impacts of traded goods and services” is presented in the table below [110]:

RACER subcriteria developed under ERA-NET SKIP Project EIPOT		
RACER Criterion	Sub-criteria	Underlying question
R - Relevant	Linkage to the project's aim	Is the assessment methodology really tracking all relevant flows? Does it enable user to quantify and assess environmental impacts of international trade?
	Policy support, identification of targets and gaps	Is the tool/methodology related to existing EU-specific policy objectives? Does it provide guidance in monitoring, strategic policy making and/or target setting? Does it quantify gaps between the current situation and specified targets? Does it react to short-term changes that can (among other things) show whether policies are having an effect?
	Identification of trends	Can the methodology/indicator be used to track changes through time? This implies that at least some input variables will require time series data (e.g. a series of annual measurements).
	Forecasting and modelling	Can the methodology/indicator be used in a predictive sense to forecast future environmental impacts or for more sophisticated modelling where the impact of different potential policies or of technology progress and/or change of patterns can be simulated? Can the assessment tool function as an early warning tool?
	Coverage of one or several environmental categories	Does the methodology allow considering only one environmental category or does it embrace all the impact categories? Is the method relevant in the sense that impacts of trade in various (all) environmental categories can be traced? In this criterion the environmental impact categories as known from the LCA approach are used: • Global warming • Stratospheric ozone depletion • Photochemical oxidant formation • Acidification • Nutrient enrichment • Ecotoxicity • Human toxicity • Radiation • Resource consumption • Land use • Waste • Effects on eco-systems and biodiversity
	DPSIR coverage	Which phase(s) of the D(riving force)-P(ressure)-S(tate)-I(mpact)-R(esponse)-Cycle is (are) covered by the examined methodology? Is it possible to expand it to other phases?

Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
Author:	EKODENGE	Version	1
Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	Scale/level of economic activity	On which level (i.e. micro/sectoral/regional/macro) does the methodology focus on? Does the methodology provide information relevant to the effective levels of application? Disaggregations – either spatial, by product or by industry – may be required for effective policy. One example for here is, if decisions are affecting trade patterns of a certain industry, is industry-level data provided by the method? But also the question concerning the supply chain of products; if the chain encompasses different countries /regions and if there are tracking possibilities on where environmental pressures take place (sector/region combinations)?
	Geographical scope	Was the methodology developed for an application in European countries or, if not, is it principally possible to adapt it for this use?
A - Accepted	Stakeholder acceptance	Has the method been endorsed/recognised by stakeholders? Can the underlying rationale and meaning of a methodology be easily understood and accepted by different stakeholder groups?
	Acceptance in academia	
	Acceptance in policy making	Has the method or results of an application been applied/tested in the development or assessment of national/regional policies? What were the experiences made?
C- Credible	Unambiguous	Do the results gained through application of the methodology convey a clear, unambiguous message? This relates to the interpretation by political decision makers (i.e. does it allow for clear conclusions to guide political action?) as well as to its interpretation by the general public (does it indeed provide the information that non-experts believe it too?)
	Repeatability	Is it possible to apply the methodology in numerous (similar but different) cases? Has it been used in different circumstances and delivered reasonable results?
	Transparency	Has the complete method been published in peer-reviewed papers and related technical reports and picked up by other researchers? A method might be completely elaborated by its authors but not been taken on by 'academia'.
	Documentation of assumptions and limitations	Are the underlying data, calculation methods and assumptions fully disclosed, interpretable and reproducible, in order to ensure a uniform application?
E - Easy	Data availability	Does the methodology require inputs of data that has already been collected (in best case in electronic form) or which still has to be generated? Is it possible to update it easily?

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17

	Technical feasibility	Is the methodology simple enough to be carried out using software and expertise appropriate to the scale of application and the typical capabilities of the institution doing the calculations? Can it be applied using standard software and hardware or does it require purchasing special equipment? Are the inputs and the calculation methodology clearly defined to avoid ambiguity and consequent error in implementation?
	Integration	Are there potential complements between the specific methodology and the others being assessed in this project? Is there the potential for further integration of the methodology with (one of) the others?
R - Robust	Defensible theory	Is the methodology based on a sound theory? Does it avoid double counting or omissions of resources used? Is it consistent in its units of measure? Does it rely on assumptions that are clearly stated and reasonable? The methodology should normally avoid the use of subjective factors to weight different components, for instance when combining various impact categories in one value.
	Sensitivity	Is there an assessment of the uncertainty of the produced data included in the methodology? Is an error estimation or calculation procedure an integral part of the study, is there an explicit sensitivity testing approach provided, or is the uncertainty of the produced data only described in general terms?
	Data quality	Does the methodology use robust real data and estimation procedures which serve for all declared purposes – on aggregated as well as on disaggregated levels?
	Reliability	What are the sources of the used data? Is the data provided by official governmental statistical offices, nongovernmental but trustworthy sources, or are there any concerns about the data source and/or the method of data gathering?
	Consistency	
	Comparability	With other results and standardisation potential
	Boundaries	Is there a clear definition of system boundaries and is it followed throughout the whole methodology? Does the boundary definition match with standard or established methods? Do the defined boundaries provide for the comparison with the results of other studies, or are recalculations required? Does the methodology cover all indirect emissions/impacts caused by the upstream production?

	Document	D2.1 Technical Report on State-of-the-art of Value Chain Assessment		
	Author:	EKODENGE	Version	1
	Reference	D2.1 CIRC-PACK ID GA 730423	Date:	31/8/17